

Fundamental limits of overparametrized shallow neural networks for supervised learning

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Abstract

We carry out an information-theoretical analysis of a two-layer neural network trained from input-output pairs generated by a teacher network with matching architecture, in overparametrized regimes. Our results come in the form of bounds relating *i*) the mutual information between training data and network weights, and *ii*) the Bayes-optimal generalization error, to the same quantities but for a simpler (generalized) linear model for which explicit expressions are rigorously known. Our bounds, which are expressed in terms of the number of training samples, input dimension and number of hidden units, yield fundamental performance limits for learning a target function with the form of a shallow neural network when limited data is available. The proof relies on rigorous tools from spin glasses and is guided by “Gaussian equivalence principles” lying at the core of numerous recent analyses of neural networks. Our results are information-theoretic (i.e. are not specific to any learning algorithm) and, importantly, cover a setting where *all* the student network parameters are trained.

Keywords: Bayesian Inference, Information theoretical limits, Gaussian equivalence principle, Shallow Neural Networks, Overparametrization, Generalization Error

MSC Classification: 68Txx , 68T07

1 Introduction

Artificial neural networks (NNs) are universal approximators [Cybenko \(1989\)](#); [Hornik et al. \(1989\)](#); [Lu et al. \(2017\)](#) with remarkable performance in supervised learning tasks such as regression or classification. In particular, modern deep neural networks, originally inspired by multilayer perceptrons [Gardner and Derrida \(1989\)](#); [Seung et al. \(1992\)](#); [Nelder and Wedderburn \(1972\)](#); [McCullagh \(1984\)](#); [Barbier et al. \(2019\)](#), achieve exceptional performance in image classification or speech recognition [Alzubaidi et al. \(2021\)](#) just to name a few examples. However, despite the important activity revolving around them, their theoretical understanding remains rather poor.

One reason for the lack of strong theoretical guarantees for realistic NN models is related to the complex interplay between at least three aspects, whose individual effects are hard to single out: their architecture, the structure inherent to the data sets on which they are trained, as well as the algorithms and optimization procedures used to do so. It is therefore of crucial interest to tackle well defined theoretical models which are rich enough to capture some of the features of real NNs while remaining theoretically tractable. In this work, we propose to analyse a teacher-student set-up from a Bayesian-optimal perspective, with random input data and dependent responses generated according to a rule based on a teacher NN. This setting has the advantage to disentangle the aforementioned three components of NN learning by allowing us to mostly focus on how the *architecture* of the NN used for learning (and data generation), and how the amount of accessible data, influence the prediction performance. More precisely, we are going to show that, in an *overparametrized regime*, we can characterize the prediction capabilities of the NN

learning a complex rule linking *unstructured* inputs to responses in the *information-theoretic optimal way*. Our results, being of an information-theoretic nature, will not depend on a specific learning procedure. On the other hand, matching Bayes-optimal generalization performance with polynomial time training algorithms remains open. This is widely believed to be not possible in general, due to the presence of possibly fundamental statistical-to-computational gaps, see e.g. [Barbier et al. \(2019\)](#). Moreover, because the inputs will be unstructured, the conclusions drawn will essentially capture architecture-dependent features of the learning and data generation process.

A key challenge one has to face when analysing NNs is the presence of non-linear activation functions, whose role is essential for the network expressivity. Models with linear activations cannot capture non-linearities, but they serve as a starting point for deeper understanding [Li and Sompolinsky \(2021\)](#). The case of a narrow hidden layer was already studied more than thirty years ago [Schwarze and Hertz \(1992\)](#); [Schwarze \(1993\)](#); [Monasson and Zecchina \(1995\)](#) and more recently in [Aubin et al. \(2018\)](#). However, in the more challenging regimes where *all layers are large and of comparable sizes* it was observed (for instance in [Hastie et al. \(2022\)](#); [Mei and Montanari \(2021\)](#); [Goldt et al. \(2020, 2022\)](#); [Hu and Lu \(2022\)](#); [Montanari and Saeed \(2022\)](#)) that certain NNs models behave like finely tuned linear models regardless of the activation type, given sufficient regularity. From these observations, a whole set of “Gaussian equivalence principles” (GEPs) have emerged as valuable tools for handling non-linear activations in both rigorous and more heuristic approaches. GEPs leverage a well-known fact in high-dimensional probability: suitably rescaled low-dimensional projections of high-dimensional vectors with weakly correlated components exhibit Gaussian behavior. Classical results [Sudakov \(1978\)](#); [Diaconis and Freedman \(1984\)](#) and recent developments [Reeves \(2017\)](#); [Meckes \(2012\)](#) support the validity of GEPs in various high-dimensional inference contexts, such as in the description of certain observables for shallow neural networks [Goldt et al. \(2020, 2022\)](#); [Hu and Lu \(2022\)](#).

However, the extent to which GEPs apply to the *information-theoretic study of NNs where all weights are learned* remains uncertain. Certain scaling regimes relating the number of data samples and network weights must cause GEPs to break down, as NNs do not always behave like linear models [Ghorbani et al. \(2020\)](#). This paper is a first step to bridging this gap by means of rigorous mathematical physics techniques developed in the study of spin glasses. We demonstrate the existence of a scaling regime for two-layer networks where GEPs are rigorously applicable, with the number of data playing a central role. As a result, we establish the information-theoretical equivalence between a two-layer NN and a generalized linear model, that hence share the same optimal generalization error.

Notations

Bold notations are reserved for vectors and matrices. By default a vector \mathbf{x} is a column vector, and its transpose \mathbf{x}^\top is therefore a row vector. Thus the usual L_2 norm $\|\mathbf{x}\|^2 = \mathbf{x}^\top \mathbf{x}$ and $\mathbf{x}\mathbf{x}^\top$ is a rank-one projector. \mathbb{E}_A is an expectation with respect to the random variable A ; \mathbb{E} is an expectation with respect to all random variables entering the ensuing expression. For a function F of one argument we denote F' its derivative, and for bounded function F we denote $\|F\|_\infty = \max_{x \in \mathbb{R}} |F(x)|$. Notations like $i \leq N$ always implicitly assume that the index i starts at 1. We often compactly write $\mathbb{E}(\dots)^2 = \mathbb{E}[(\dots)^2] \geq (\mathbb{E}(\dots))^2 = \mathbb{E}^2(\dots)$ and similarly for other functions, we denote equivalently $\mathbb{E}[f(\dots)]$ and $\mathbb{E}f(\dots)$. For any functions f and g , $f = O(g)$ means that there exists a constant K such that $|f| \leq K|g|$; in other words we simply denote $O(g) := O(|g|)$ where in the r.h.s. we use the standard big O notation. Hence, taken for instance a Gaussian r.v. $Z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$, $f = O(Z)$ does *not* imply $\mathbb{E}f = 0$, but rather $|\mathbb{E}f| \leq \mathbb{E}|f| \leq K\mathbb{E}|Z|$. The non-negative constant c will denote a general constant that does not depend on any parameter of the initial model and can vary from line to line.

Acknowledgements

We wish to thank Marco Mondelli for suggesting meaningful references, and Rosalba Pacelli and Pietro Rotondo for fruitful clarifications on [Li and Sompolinsky \(2021\)](#); [Ariosto et al. \(2022\)](#).

Statements and Declarations

The Authors declare no competing interests.

Funding

The authors were funded by the European Union (ERC, CHORAL, project number 101039794). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Council. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

2 Setting and main results

2.1 Bayesian-optimal learning of a shallow network in the teacher-student set-up

We consider supervised learning with a Bayesian two-layer neural network in a teacher-student setup, with matched architecture for teacher (i.e., data-generating) and student (i.e., trained) models. To be precise, let the dataset be $\mathcal{D}_n = \{(\mathbf{X}_\mu, Y_\mu)\}_{\mu=1}^n$, with inputs $\mathbf{X}_\mu \in \mathbb{R}^d$ and responses $Y_\mu \in \mathbb{R}$. The Y_μ could also be taken from \mathbb{R}^K with K independent of d, p, n without much changes. The teacher network generates the responses according to the following rule:

$$Y_\mu = f\left(\frac{\mathbf{a}^{*\top}}{\sqrt{p}}\varphi\left(\frac{\mathbf{W}^*\mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}}\right); \mathbf{A}_\mu\right) + \sqrt{\Delta}Z_\mu. \quad (1)$$

Here, $\mathbf{a}^* \in \mathbb{R}^p$ and $\mathbf{W}^* \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times d}$. The readout function f can include stochasticity, modeled through its second argument \mathbf{A}_μ which are independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) random variables in \mathbb{R}^k with k fixed, whose common distribution is denoted by P_A . Whenever it is not specified, real functions are applied component-wise to vectors, such as the non linearities f, φ . We assume the following regularity hypotheses:

H1) The activation function $\varphi : \mathbb{R} \mapsto \mathbb{R}$, $\varphi \in C^2$ is c -Lipschitz for some absolute constant c , is such that $\mathbb{E}\varphi(z) = 0$ for $z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$, and has bounded second and third derivatives.

H2) The readout function f as well as its first and second derivatives are P_A -almost surely bounded.

We draw the independent inputs $\mathbf{X}_\mu \stackrel{\text{iid}}{\sim} \mathcal{N}(0, I_d)$ from the standard Gaussian measure. Furthermore, Gaussian label noise $Z_\mu \stackrel{\text{iid}}{\sim} \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ is added in (1), whose variance is tuned by $\Delta > 0$. Introducing the output kernel

$$P_{\text{out}}(y | x) := \int P_A(d\mathbf{A}) \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\Delta}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2\Delta}(y - f(x; \mathbf{A}))^2\right), \quad (2)$$

one can see that the random outputs are generated independently, conditionally on the teacher parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}^* = (\mathbf{a}^*, \mathbf{W}^*)$ and the inputs, as

$$Y_\mu \sim P_{\text{out}}\left(\cdot \mid \frac{\mathbf{a}^{*\top}}{\sqrt{p}}\varphi\left(\frac{\mathbf{W}^*\mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}}\right)\right). \quad (3)$$

The probability distribution for the weights of the teacher network are drawn from a centered Gaussian factorized prior distribution. Taking them with different variances is possible but it does not add much to the result, so we consider them all equal to one for our purposes: $a_i^*, W_{ij}^* \stackrel{\text{iid}}{\sim} \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$. The same Gaussian law is used as prior distribution for the Bayesian student neural network model.

In this paper we deal with Bayesian learning in the so-called *Bayes-optimal setting*, which is the proper framework to quantify the fundamental performance limits of learning neural network target functions. Concretely, the Bayes-optimal scenario corresponds to a realizable matched setting where the student network has exactly the same architecture as the teacher network used to generate the responses in the data \mathcal{D}_n . The analysis in this setting therefore yields the best information-theoretically achievable student's generalization performance whenever optimally trained, namely, when using Bayesian learning based on the posterior distribution of the student's parameters. As a consequence,

our results lay down fundamental upper bounds for the performance of any neural network (Bayesian or not) trained in any possible manner (including empirical risk minimization rather than Bayesian learning) on the

data generated by a teacher neural network. Moreover, both the readout and internal hidden layer of the student network are trained, with a number of hidden units, training samples, and input dimension that can diverge.

More formally, a student network is said to be Bayes-optimal if it employs the same output kernel P_{out} as used by the teacher network, or equivalently same number of layers and layers widths, readout f and activation φ , label noise variance Δ , as well as same prior law for its weights. Bayes-optimal learning is then based on the Bayes posterior of the network parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta} = (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{W})$ which reads

$$dP(\boldsymbol{\theta} | \mathcal{D}_n) = \frac{1}{\mathcal{Z}(\mathcal{D}_n)} \prod_{\mu=1}^n P_{\text{out}}\left(Y_\mu | \frac{\mathbf{a}^\top}{\sqrt{p}} \varphi\left(\frac{\mathbf{W}\mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}}\right)\right) D\boldsymbol{\theta} \quad (4)$$

where for brevity

$$D\boldsymbol{\theta} := \prod_{i=1}^p \frac{da_i}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{a_i^2}{2}} \prod_{i=1}^p \prod_{j=1}^d \frac{dW_{ij}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{w_{ij}^2}{2}} =: D\mathbf{a}D\mathbf{W}. \quad (5)$$

We will often use the notation D for densities of objects whose entries are i.i.d. standard Gaussian variables. The normalization of the posterior distribution will be referred to as *partition function*:

$$\mathcal{Z}(\mathcal{D}_n) := \int D\boldsymbol{\theta} \exp\left(\sum_{\mu=1}^n u_{Y_\mu}(s_\mu)\right) \quad (6)$$

where we have introduced the two further definitions $u_y(x) = \log P_{\text{out}}(y | x)$ and

$$s_\mu := \frac{\mathbf{a}^\top}{\sqrt{p}} \varphi\left(\frac{\mathbf{W}\mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}}\right), \quad S_\mu := \frac{\mathbf{a}^{*\top}}{\sqrt{p}} \varphi\left(\frac{\mathbf{W}^*\mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}}\right), \quad (7)$$

which correspond to the student and teacher models, respectively. Note that the partition function is random through the randomness of the dataset \mathcal{D}_n . Then, (optimal) Bayesian learning means that the predictor $\hat{Y}_{\text{Bayes}}(\mathbf{X}_{\text{new}})$ of the response associated with a fresh input test sample corresponds to the mean of the Bayes posterior distribution of the response given the training data:

$$\hat{Y}_{\text{Bayes}}(\mathbf{X}_{\text{new}}) := \mathbb{E}[Y_{\text{new}} | \mathcal{D}_n, \mathbf{X}_{\text{new}}] = \int dY Y P_{\text{out}}\left(Y | \frac{\mathbf{a}^\top}{\sqrt{p}} \varphi\left(\frac{\mathbf{W}\mathbf{X}_{\text{new}}}{\sqrt{d}}\right)\right) dP(\boldsymbol{\theta} | \mathcal{D}_n). \quad (8)$$

We will sometimes employ the language of statistical mechanics. In particular we interpret the posterior distribution as a Boltzmann-Gibbs measure over degrees of freedom which are the network weights. We shall denote the expectations w.r.t. the posterior with the so-called Gibbs brackets $\langle \cdot \rangle$. For future convenience we introduce also its replicated version: for a function g dependent of k copies $(\boldsymbol{\theta}_b)_{b \leq k}$ of the parameters,

$$\langle g \rangle^{\otimes k} := \frac{1}{\mathcal{Z}(\mathcal{D}_n)^k} \int \prod_{b=1}^k D\boldsymbol{\theta}_b \prod_{\mu=1}^n P_{\text{out}}\left(Y_\mu | \frac{\mathbf{a}_b^\top}{\sqrt{p}} \varphi\left(\frac{\mathbf{W}_b \mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}}\right)\right) g((\boldsymbol{\theta}_b)_{b \leq k}), \quad (9)$$

that, with a slight abuse of notation, will still be denoted by $\langle \cdot \rangle$. From the above definition we see that the replicated Boltzmann-Gibbs measure is factorized for a given realization of the dataset, interpreted as quenched randomness in the analogy with spin glasses [Mézard et al. \(1987\)](#). Hence, *replicas*, namely i.i.d. samples from the posterior measure, are independent conditionally on \mathcal{D}_n . However, when computing so-called quenched averages $\mathbb{E}\langle \cdot \rangle$ a further expectation \mathbb{E} is taken w.r.t. the quenched data which couples the replicas.

One of the main object of interest is the *free entropy* (i.e., log-partition function) per sample, which is nothing else than minus the Shannon entropy $H(\mathcal{D}_n)$ of the data distribution per sample:

$$\bar{f}_n := \frac{1}{n} \mathbb{E} \log \mathcal{Z}(\mathcal{D}_n) = -\frac{1}{n} H(\mathcal{D}_n), \quad (10)$$

where the expectation \mathbb{E} is w.r.t. to the training data $\mathcal{D}_n = \{(\mathbf{X}_\mu, Y_\mu)\}_{\mu=1}^n$. The normalization by n is natural given that the number of terms in the “energy” defined by the exponent in (6) is precisely n . The data has a joint law that can be written in terms of the output kernel

$$\begin{aligned} dP(\mathcal{D}_n) &= \prod_{\mu=1}^n \left(\prod_{j=1}^d \frac{dX_{\mu j}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{x_{\mu j}^2}{2}} \right) dY_\mu \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{a}^*, \mathbf{w}^*} \prod_{\mu=1}^n P_{\text{out}}(Y_\mu | S_\mu) \\ &=: \prod_{\mu=1}^n D\mathbf{X}_\mu dY_\mu \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{a}^*, \mathbf{w}^*} \exp \left(\sum_{\mu=1}^n u_{Y_\mu}(S_\mu) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Two observations are in order. First, the samples, indexed by μ , are not independent because the responses were all drawn from the teacher, even though the \mathbf{X}_μ 's are independently generated. Second, except for the presence of differentials on the quenched variables this expression is very similar to the partition function (6). This is due to the Bayes-optimality of the student network and has some pragmatic consequences, such as the Nishimori identities which will be key for the proof. To introduce them formally, consider a generic inference problem where a Bayes-optimal statistician observes \mathbf{Y} that is a random function of some ground truth signal \mathbf{X}^* : $\mathbf{Y} \sim P_{Y|X}(\mathbf{X}^*)$. Then, using Bayes' rule (see also [Lelarge and Miolane \(2017\)](#) for the proof), one can prove the following:

Proposition 1 (Nishimori identity). *For any bounded function f of the signal \mathbf{X}^* , the data \mathbf{Y} and of conditionally i.i.d. samples from the posterior $\mathbf{x}^j \sim P_{X|Y}(\cdot | \mathbf{Y})$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$, we have that*

$$\mathbb{E}\langle f(\mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{X}^*, \mathbf{x}^2, \dots, \mathbf{x}^n) \rangle = \mathbb{E}\langle f(\mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{x}^1, \mathbf{x}^2, \dots, \mathbf{x}^n) \rangle \quad (12)$$

where the bracket notation $\langle \cdot \rangle$ is used for the joint expectation over the posterior samples $(\mathbf{x}^j)_{j \leq n}$, \mathbb{E} is over the signal \mathbf{X}^* and data \mathbf{Y} .

Furthermore, we point out that the Gaussian prior assumption is not only a technical requirement, but is also related to standard empirical risk minimization with L^2 norm regulators, as done explicitly in [Gerace et al. \(2020\)](#); [Pacelli et al. \(2023\)](#) for instance. In fact, one could define a free entropy of a statistical mechanics model whose ground state, obtained with a 0 temperature limit, can be identified with the minimum of the empirical risk. The cost function, or Hamiltonian, of this model would indeed contain some Gaussian penalties that act as norm regulators on the weights.

Finally, let us comment briefly on our assumptions. For the sake of simplicity we did not include trainable biases in the definition of our NN model, which also matches the setting of [Cui et al. \(2023\)](#). A bias on the readout can easily be re-absorbed in the readout function definition, but learnable biases on the hidden neurons, instead, introduce non-trivial complications in the analysis.

Concerning the requirement $\mathbb{E}_{z \sim \mathcal{N}(0,1)} \varphi(z) = 0$, it is trivially satisfied for all odd activation functions, but not satisfied for many popular activations, such as ReLU. We have heuristic reasons to believe that even when φ has a nonzero 0-th Hermite coefficient, the main conclusions remain valid. Indeed, in such cases one can extract the mean of the activation, which produces an additional term of the form $\mu \mathbf{a}^* \mathbf{1} / \sqrt{p}$, where $\mu = \mathbb{E}_{z \sim \mathcal{N}(0,1)} \varphi(z)$ and $\mathbf{1}$ denotes the all-ones vector. While \mathbf{a}^* cannot be recovered exactly, the term $\mu \mathbf{a}^* \mathbf{1} / \sqrt{p}$ can, asymptotically, via maximum likelihood when n diverges. Thus the student network, which has access to the full dataset, effectively knows this value and it can be removed from the learning problem.

We instead expect that the regularity hypothesis can be relaxed via a continuity argument, by approximating activation functions via compactly supported C^∞ functions, similar to what is done in [Barbier et al. \(2019\)](#). Since this paper's purpose is to lay the ground for a self contained proof of GEPs in Bayes-optimal learning, the relaxation of these technical requirements is left for future investigation.

2.2 An information-theoretically equivalent generalized linear model

We now introduce an another model known as Generalized Linear Model (GLM) [Nelder and Wedderburn \(1972\)](#); [McCullagh \(1984\)](#); [Barbier et al. \(2019\)](#), which can be represented as a one layer neural network and which is thus a generalization of the classical perceptron [Gardner and Derrida \(1989\)](#); [Seung et al. \(1992\)](#). One particular instance of the GLM turns out to be deeply connected to the setting with shallow networks introduced in the previous section. In this model the responses are generated independently

conditionally on the inputs as

$$Y_\mu^\circ = f\left(\rho \frac{\mathbf{v}^{*\top} \mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}} + \sqrt{\epsilon} \xi_\mu^*; \mathbf{A}_\mu\right) + \sqrt{\Delta} Z_\mu, \quad \text{or} \quad Y_\mu^\circ \sim P_{\text{out}}\left(\cdot \mid \rho \frac{\mathbf{v}^{*\top} \mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}} + \sqrt{\epsilon} \xi_\mu^*\right) \quad (13)$$

where $\mathbf{v}^* = (v_j^*)_{j \leq d} \in \mathbb{R}^d$, $v_j^* \stackrel{\text{iid}}{\sim} \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$, $\xi_\mu^* \stackrel{\text{iid}}{\sim} \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ all independently and the rest is as before. With respect to the two-layer neural network, the non-linearity brought by the middle layer has been replaced by a linear model with an additional effective Gaussian noise ξ_μ^* . ρ and $\epsilon \geq 0$ are two real parameters that will be specified later. This connection between the Bayes-optimal learning of neural networks and this GLM was recently conjectured in [Cui et al. \(2023\)](#) based on the replica method and the application of Gaussian equivalences. Our results vindicate their conjecture but for different scaling regimes relating the diverging parameters d, p, n . We are going to further comment on this point later on.

All the above construction can be repeated for the generalized linear model. From now on, quantities characterized by a $^\circ$ superscript will refer to the GLM. For starters, we denote the dataset generated through (13) by $\mathcal{D}_n^\circ := \{(\mathbf{X}_\mu, Y_\mu^\circ)\}_{\mu=1}^n$. Let

$$s_\mu^\circ = \rho \frac{\mathbf{v}^\top \mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}} + \sqrt{\epsilon} \xi_\mu, \quad S_\mu^\circ = \rho \frac{\mathbf{v}^{*\top} \mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}} + \sqrt{\epsilon} \xi_\mu^*$$

and $D\xi = \prod_\mu D\xi_\mu$. The expectation under the GLM posterior of any bounded test function g of k ‘‘replicas’’ (i.e., conditionally on the data i.i.d. copies) $(\mathbf{v}_b, \xi_b)_{b \leq k}$ reads

$$\langle g \rangle^{\circ \otimes k} := \frac{1}{\mathcal{Z}^\circ(\mathcal{D}_n^\circ)^k} \int \prod_{b=1}^k D\mathbf{v}_b D\xi_b \prod_{\mu=1}^n P_{\text{out}}\left(Y_\mu^\circ \mid \rho \frac{\mathbf{v}_b^\top \mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}} + \sqrt{\epsilon} \xi_{b\mu}\right) g((\mathbf{v}_b, \xi_b)_{b \leq k}), \quad (14)$$

with $\mathcal{Z}^\circ(\mathcal{D}_n^\circ)$ the GLM posterior normalization. As before, the free entropy reads

$$\bar{f}_n^\circ := \frac{1}{n} \mathbb{E} \log \mathcal{Z}^\circ(\mathcal{D}_n^\circ) = \frac{1}{n} \mathbb{E} \log \int D\mathbf{v} D\xi \exp\left(\sum_{\mu=1}^n u_{Y_\mu^\circ}(s_\mu^\circ)\right). \quad (15)$$

Finally, we write the distribution of the dataset, that is used for the quenched average in the above formula:

$$\begin{aligned} dP(\mathcal{D}_n^\circ) &= \prod_{\mu=1}^n \left(\prod_{j=1}^d \frac{dX_{\mu j}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{x_{\mu j}^2}{2}} \right) dY_\mu^\circ \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{v}^*, \xi^*} \prod_{\mu=1}^n P_{\text{out}}(Y_\mu^\circ \mid S_\mu^\circ) \\ &=: \prod_{\mu=1}^n D\mathbf{X}_\mu dY_\mu \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{v}^*, \xi^*} \exp\left(\sum_{\mu=1}^n u_{Y_\mu^\circ}(S_\mu^\circ)\right) \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

and the optimal Bayesian predictor is

$$\hat{Y}_{\text{Bayes}}^\circ(\mathbf{X}_{\text{new}}) := \mathbb{E}[Y_{\text{new}}^\circ \mid \mathcal{D}_n^\circ, \mathbf{X}_{\text{new}}] = \int dY Y P_{\text{out}}\left(Y \mid \rho \frac{\mathbf{v}^\top \mathbf{X}_{\text{new}}}{\sqrt{d}} + \sqrt{\epsilon} \xi\right) dP(\mathbf{v}, \xi \mid \mathcal{D}_n^\circ). \quad (17)$$

2.3 Results

Our first theorem concerns the equivalence between the Bayes-optimal learning of the neural network and GLM models at the level of free entropy. Letting $Z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ we denote $\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)} g := \mathbb{E}g(Z)$.

Theorem 2 (Free entropy equivalence). *Let*

$$\rho := \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)} \varphi' \quad \text{and} \quad \epsilon^2 := \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)} \varphi^2 - \rho^2, \quad (18)$$

and suppose [H1](#)) and [H2](#)) hold. Then

$$|\bar{f}_n - \bar{f}_n^\circ| = O\left(\sqrt{\left(1 + \frac{n}{d}\right)\left(\frac{n}{p} + \frac{n}{d^{3/2}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{d}}\right)}\right). \quad (19)$$

From the previous statement we can identify the scaling regime for which the equivalence holds, namely, when the right hand side of [\(19\)](#) goes to 0. From now on we shall denote by

$$\widetilde{\lim} g_{d,p,n} := \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} g_{d_i, p_i, n_i}$$

where $(d_i, p_i, n_i)_i$ is any sequence of triplets of integers such that

$$\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \left(1 + \frac{n_i}{d_i}\right) \left(\frac{n_i}{p_i} + \frac{n_i}{d_i^{3/2}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{d_i}}\right) = 0. \quad (20)$$

As a corollary we have the matching of the mutual informations between the dataset \mathcal{D}_n and the network weights in the same limit. For the two-layer neural network the mutual information is related to the free entropy through the following expression (H is the Shannon entropy)

$$\frac{1}{n} I_n(\boldsymbol{\theta}^*; \mathcal{D}_n) = \frac{1}{n} H(\mathcal{D}_n) - \frac{1}{n} H(\mathcal{D}_n | \boldsymbol{\theta}^*) = -\bar{f}_n + \mathbb{E} \log P_{\text{out}}\left(Y_1 | \frac{\mathbf{a}^{*\top}}{\sqrt{p}} \varphi\left(\frac{\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{X}_1}{\sqrt{d}}\right)\right), \quad (21)$$

whereas for the equivalent GLM we have

$$\frac{1}{n} I_n^\circ(\boldsymbol{\theta}^{\circ*}; \mathcal{D}_n^\circ) = -\bar{f}_n^\circ + \mathbb{E} \log P_{\text{out}}\left(Y_1 | \rho \frac{\mathbf{v}^{*\top} \mathbf{X}_1}{\sqrt{d}} + \sqrt{\epsilon} \xi_1^*\right). \quad (22)$$

Considering that the teacher weights and inputs are Gaussian we have in law

$$\frac{\mathbf{a}^{*\top}}{\sqrt{p}} \varphi\left(\frac{\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{X}_1}{\sqrt{d}}\right) \stackrel{\text{D}}{=} Z \sqrt{\frac{1}{p} \left\| \varphi\left(\frac{\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{X}_1}{\sqrt{d}}\right) \right\|^2} \quad (23)$$

with $Z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ and $\|\cdot\|$ is the standard L^2 norm for vectors. Therefore, it is clear that the randomness in \mathbf{W}^* and \mathbf{X}_1 will disappear in the limit. A similar equality holds for the GLM:

$$\rho \frac{\mathbf{v}^{*\top} \mathbf{X}_1}{\sqrt{d}} + \sqrt{\epsilon} \xi_1^* \stackrel{\text{D}}{=} Z \sqrt{\rho^2 \frac{\|\mathbf{X}_1\|^2}{d} + \epsilon}. \quad (24)$$

Our goal is now to show that the arguments under square root both tend to $\rho^2 + \epsilon = \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)} \varphi^2$ in the limit, and that we can plug this result inside the last terms in [\(21\)](#) and [\(22\)](#), with a control on the error we make. To this end, define

$$S_d(t) = \sqrt{t \rho^2 \left(\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_1\|^2}{d} - 1\right) + \epsilon + \rho^2}, \quad \text{or} \quad S_d(t) = \sqrt{t \left(\frac{1}{p} \left\| \varphi\left(\frac{\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{X}_1}{\sqrt{d}}\right) \right\|^2 - \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)} \varphi^2\right) + \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)} \varphi^2} \quad (25)$$

and

$$\Psi(t) := \mathbb{E} \int dY P_{\text{out}}(Y | Z S_d(t)) \log P_{\text{out}}(Y | Z S_d(t)). \quad (26)$$

Using the properties later described in [Lemma 5](#) and the definition of P_{out} in [\(2\)](#), under assumptions [\(H1\)](#)-[\(H2\)](#) one can readily verify that

$$|\dot{\Psi}(t)| \leq C(f) \mathbb{E} |Z| |\dot{S}_d(t)|, \quad (27)$$

where $C(f)$ is a constant depending on f . From this bound, by the fundamental theorem of integral calculus, we have

$$|\Psi(1) - \Psi(0)| \leq C(f) \int_0^1 dt \mathbb{E} |\dot{S}_d(t)| \leq C(f) \begin{cases} \frac{\mathbb{E} \|\varphi(\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{X}_1 / \sqrt{d})\|^2 / p - \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)} \varphi^2}{\sqrt{\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)} \varphi^2}} & \text{for the 2-layer NN} \\ \rho^2 \frac{\mathbb{E} \|\mathbf{X}_1\|^2 / d - 1}{\sqrt{\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)} \varphi^2}} & \text{for the GLM} \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

The remainder for the two-layer NN is $O(p^{-1/2} + d^{-1/4})$ whereas for the GLM we have $O(d^{-1/2})$. Finally, thanks to the previous argument

$$\frac{1}{n} I_n(\boldsymbol{\theta}^*; \mathcal{D}_n) = -\bar{f}_n + \Psi(\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)} \varphi^2) + O(p^{-1/2} + d^{-1/4}), \quad (29)$$

$$\frac{1}{n} I_n^\circ(\boldsymbol{\theta}^{\circ*}; \mathcal{D}_n^\circ) = -\bar{f}_n^\circ + \Psi(\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)} \varphi^2) + O(d^{-1/2}), \quad (30)$$

where

$$\Psi(\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)} \varphi^2) := \Psi(0) = \mathbb{E} \int dY P_{\text{out}}(Y | Z \sqrt{\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)} \varphi^2}) \log P_{\text{out}}(Y | Z \sqrt{\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)} \varphi^2}). \quad (31)$$

Hence, we have just proved the information theoretical equivalence:

Corollary 3 (Mutual information equivalence). *Under the same hypothesis of Theorem 2 the following holds:*

$$\left| \frac{1}{n} I_n(\boldsymbol{\theta}^*; \mathcal{D}_n) - \frac{1}{n} I_n^\circ(\boldsymbol{\theta}^{\circ*}; \mathcal{D}_n^\circ) \right| = O\left(\sqrt{\left(1 + \frac{n}{d}\right) \left(\frac{n}{p} + \frac{n}{d^{3/2}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{d}}\right)}\right). \quad (32)$$

The performance of the neural network is quantified using the generalization error on test data using the square loss. The Bayes-optimal generalization error thus reads

$$\mathcal{E}_n := \mathbb{E} (Y_{\text{new}} - \mathbb{E}[Y_{\text{new}} | \mathcal{D}_n, \mathbf{X}_{\text{new}}])^2. \quad (33)$$

The outer expectation is intended w.r.t. the training data set and the test sample which is generated independently from the training data according to the same teacher model. The GLM Bayes-optimal generalization error \mathcal{E}_n° is defined similarly but considering the GLM teacher-student setting described in the previous section.

As a consequence of the proof technique of Theorem 2 it is possible to show the following equivalence at the level of the generalization error, which is a standard measure of performance of a neural network tasked with classification or regression. The proof can be found in Section 5.

Theorem 4 (Generalization error equivalence). *Under the same hypothesis of Theorem 2 the following holds:*

$$\widetilde{\lim} |\mathcal{E}_n - \mathcal{E}_n^\circ| = 0, \quad (34)$$

i.e., the shallow neural network and noisy GLM settings lead to the same Bayes-optimal generalization error in any high-dimensional limit such that (20) holds.

Remark 1. Our results combined with those of Barbier et al. (2019) for the GLM provide explicit rigorous formulas for the mutual information and Bayes-optimal generalization error for the Bayesian neural network studied in this paper. We stress that our bounds hold for any n, p, d , and the equivalences hold in the limit also for $n = O(d)$, which is the non-trivial scaling for the GLM, provided that $p \gg d, n$.

The previous theorem states that the Bayes-optimal generalization error of a two-layer NN, which is trained on the dataset \mathcal{D}_n generated by a teacher two-layer NN with same architecture, equals that of a noisy GLM trained on the dataset \mathcal{D}_n° generated by a matched teacher GLM. However, we cannot deduce from this that the two-layer NN trained using the GLM teacher dataset \mathcal{D}_n° , or viceversa, achieves the Bayes-optimal generalization error. It would be interesting to investigate this aspect in the future.

Figure 1 Standard neural network architectures analyzed in the literature, classified according to how scale their layers widths (large diverging layers are depicted with many neurons, those which are much smaller or of fixed size have one or two neurons), and whether the internal weights are trainable (red edges) or completely fixed and not trained (blue edges). (1) represents a *generalized linear model* (also called *perceptron*), (2) corresponds to *committee machines*, with large input size and small (finite) hidden layer; (3) and (4) are examples of *mean field* regime, where the input size is small while the hidden layer is large; in particular model (4) corresponds to the *random feature model*; (5) and (6) represent the challenging *linear-width* regimes. Our results cover, e.g., models belonging to the regimes (6), and (3) when $p \gg d \gg n \gg 1$.

2.4 Related works

We provide here a (non-exhaustive) overview of some theoretical contributions about NNs, organized according to how their internal widths scale compared to the inputs dimension, and whether the internal weights are trainable or not, see Figure 1.

In [Barbier et al. \(2019\)](#) the authors were able to rigorously prove a closed formula for the mutual information between weights and dataset in a teacher-student set-up for the GLM, and consequently also its Bayes-optimal generalization error. The GLM and the committee machine have a long history in the statistical physics literature. We defer the reader to the non-exhaustive list of contributions [Barkai et al. \(1992\)](#); [Engel et al. \(1992\)](#); [Schwarze \(1993\)](#); [Schwarze and Hertz \(1992, 1993\)](#); [Monasson and Zecchina \(1995\)](#); [Saad and Solla \(1995\)](#); [Mato and Parga \(1992\)](#); [Engel and Van den Broeck \(2001\)](#); [Aubin et al. \(2018\)](#); [Baldassi et al. \(2019\)](#); [Goldt et al. \(2020,?, 2022\)](#). In both models, the challenging (and thus nontrivial) scaling regime is $d = O(n)$ and $p = O(1)$ (or zero, in the case of the perceptron/GLM).

When the number of hidden units diverges, instead, we have a remarkable series of works on online learning via Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) [Nitanda and Suzuki \(2017\)](#); [Sirignano and Spiliopoulos \(2020\)](#); [Araújo et al. \(2019\)](#); [Nguyen \(2019\)](#); [Nguyen and Pham \(2023\)](#); [Mei et al. \(2018, 2019\)](#); [Chizat and Bach \(2018\)](#); [Rotskoff and Vanden-Eijnden \(2022\)](#); [Wu et al. \(2022\)](#); [Javanmard et al. \(2020\)](#); [Shevchenko et al. \(2022\)](#); [Shevchenko and Mondelli \(2020\)](#); [Mei et al. \(2019\)](#). In online learning, the student network sees one sample at a time, whereas in Bayes-optimal learning the whole dataset is jointly exploited. Hence, the mean-field analyses of SGD differ from the information-theoretical one.

In [Mei et al. \(2019\)](#), the authors argue that when few samples are provided during training, the weights can be modeled as frozen at initialization. This behavior is at the basis of the Neural Tangent Kernel of [Jacot et al. \(2021\)](#), and random feature models and lazy training regimes ([Rahimi and Recht, 2007](#); [Li and Yuan, 2017](#); [Rudi and Rosasco, 2017](#); [Bach, 2017](#); [Li and Liang, 2018](#); [Allen-Zhu et al., 2019](#); [Du et al., 2019a,b](#); [Lee et al., 2020](#); [Arora et al., 2019](#); [Huang and Yau, 2020](#); [Mei and Montanari, 2021](#); [Ghorbani et al., 2021](#); [Montanari and Zhong, 2022](#); [Gerace et al., 2020](#); [d’Ascoli et al., 2020](#); [Geiger et al., 2020](#); [Dhifallah and Lu, 2020](#); [Bordelon et al., 2020](#); [Hu and Lu, 2022](#); [Schröder et al., 2024](#); [Bosch et al., 2023](#); [Schröder et al., 2023](#)).

A contribution where all the networks weights are learnable is [Li and Sompolinsky \(2021\)](#), where the authors tackled the learning problem of deep linear networks whose width is proportional to the input dimension, see also [Zavatone-Veth et al. \(2022\)](#). Linearity allows to integrate subsequently all the dynamical degrees of freedom (i.e. the learnable weights). Subsequently, the challenging *proportional regime*, in which the number of training examples n and the sizes of all layers (d_ℓ) diverge simultaneously and in a proportional way, was studied for non-linear networks in [Pacelli et al. \(2023\)](#); [Naveh and Ringel \(2021\)](#); [Seroussi et al. \(2023\)](#); [Aiudi et al. \(2025\)](#); [Bassetti et al. \(2025\)](#); [Rubin et al. \(2025\)](#). In this paper we refer to this regime as *overparameterized*, as the number of data is small compared to the number of learnable parameters. The aforementioned works show that *some* feature learning happens, in the sense that the kernel learnt by the network adapts to the data w.r.t. to the fixed kernel that emerges in the infinite width limit described by the neural network Gaussian processes ([Neal, 1996](#); [Williams, 1996](#); [Lee et al., 2018](#); [Matthews et al., 2018](#); [Hanin, 2023](#)).

Still in the proportional regime but closer to our setting, the work [Cui et al. \(2023\)](#) conjectures a formula for the Bayes-optimal generalization error of a deep neural network using the replica method ([Mézard et al., 1987](#)). One key ingredient of their analysis is a “deep Gaussian equivalence principle” conjecture, which here we were to partially prove. See Conclusions and perspectives for some further details on the matter.

Let us finally mention the analyses of the multi-layer inference models [Aubin et al. \(2020, 2019\)](#), and especially the multi-layer GLM of [Gabrié et al. \(2018\)](#); [Chen and Xia \(2023\)](#). Although in the latter the weights are fixed, and thus not learnable as in our setting, it shares some common challenges due to the multi-layer structure, especially related to the concentration properties w.r.t. the quenched randomness of the model.

2.5 A small numerical experiment

In our paper we discuss the performance of the “equilibrium” samples from the posterior measure (4). It is thus interesting to see how the performance of other algorithms, such as SGD, compares to that of the Bayes-optimal estimator in terms of generalization for this learning problem. Therefore, we trained a two-layer neural network on the synthetic dataset generated by a matched teacher by means of the ADAM optimizer. Both teacher and student networks have a rather wide hidden layer, which is 8 times larger than the input dimension, even though, as we mention in the conclusion, and as conjectured in [Cui et al. \(2023\)](#), we expect the equivalence of generalization errors to hold also at the scale $p = O(d)$.

Figure 2 Generalization error $-\Delta$ as a function of $\frac{n}{d} \rightarrow \alpha$. The solid curve is $\mathcal{E}(\alpha) - \Delta$ in (37), whereas points and error bars refer to ADAM run with: ≤ 2000 gradient updates, batch size $\lceil n/3 \rceil$, initial learning rate 0.005, weight decay 0.01, input size $d = 50$, hidden layer width $p = 400$, label noise $\Delta = 0.1$, tanh as activation function, and linear readout as in Sect. 2.5.

For the sake of simplicity we took a linear readout, namely

$$Y_\mu = \frac{\mathbf{a}^* \boldsymbol{\tau}}{\sqrt{p}} \varphi\left(\frac{\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}}\right) + \sqrt{\Delta} Z_\mu \quad (35)$$

with $Z_\mu \stackrel{\text{iid}}{\sim} \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ is the label noise, whose intensity is tuned by Δ . Equivalently, $P_{\text{out}}(y | x) = \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2\Delta}(y - x)^2\right) / \sqrt{2\pi\Delta}$.

Corollary 4 predicts that, in the limit $\widetilde{\lim}$, the Bayes-optimal generalization error matches that of a GLM where P_{out} is replaced by

$$\tilde{P}_{\text{out}}(y | x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi(\Delta + \epsilon)}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2(\Delta + \epsilon)}(y - \rho x)^2\right). \quad (36)$$

Using the formulae in [Barbier et al. \(2019\)](#), in the hypothesis that $n/d \rightarrow \alpha$, for this GLM the limiting Bayes-optimal generalization error reads

$$\mathcal{E}(\alpha) - \Delta = \epsilon + \rho^2(1 - q(\alpha)) \quad (37)$$

with $q = q(\alpha)$ solving the system of equations

$$q = \frac{r}{1+r}, \quad r = \frac{\alpha\rho^2}{\Delta + \epsilon + \rho^2(1-q)}. \quad (38)$$

In Figure 2 we plot $\mathcal{E}(\alpha) - \Delta$, and compare it to the performance that a properly tuned SGD would attain for a small size experiment. The plot highlights how the generalization error of SGD, when halved, follows reasonably well the optimal prediction $\mathcal{E}(\alpha)$. This phenomenon was also observed recently in more detail in Maillard et al. (2024); Barbier et al. (2025) in other scaling regimes of data and network's size. These experiments seem to suggest that the weights obtained via SGD resemble those of a Gibbs sample from the posterior measure. In fact the so-called *Gibbs error* (i.e. the one obtained using a Gibbs sample for a *one-shot* estimator) is provably twice the Bayes-optimal generalization error Barbier et al. (2019).

3 Proof of Theorem 2

3.1 The interpolating model

Our proof is based on the interpolation method, introduced in the seminal papers Guerra and Toninelli (2002); Guerra (2003). This method is a very effective tool whenever a comparison between two high dimensional models is needed. The idea is that of introducing an interpolating model, for any $t \in [0, 1]$, that at its ends $t = 0$ and $t = 1$ matches the two models to be compared. In analogy with Barbier et al. (2019), we shall interpolate at the level of the variables s_μ, S_μ :

$$S_{t\mu} := \sqrt{1-t} \frac{\mathbf{a}^{*\top}}{\sqrt{p}} \varphi\left(\frac{\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}}\right) + \sqrt{t} \rho \frac{\mathbf{v}^{*\top} \mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}} + \sqrt{t\epsilon} \xi_\mu^*, \quad (39)$$

$$s_{t\mu} := \sqrt{1-t} \frac{\mathbf{a}^\top}{\sqrt{p}} \varphi\left(\frac{\mathbf{W} \mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}}\right) + \sqrt{t} \rho \frac{\mathbf{v}^\top \mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}} + \sqrt{t\epsilon} \xi_\mu. \quad (40)$$

We thus introduce an interpolating teacher and interpolating student, such that the second is Bayes-optimal for any $t \in [0, 1]$. This allows us to use the so-called Nishimori identities of Appendix A uniformly in t .

The interpolating teacher network shall produce the $\mu = 1, \dots, n$ conditionally independent responses

$$Y_{t\mu} \sim P_{\text{out}}(\cdot | S_{t\mu}), \quad (41)$$

where the output kernel is unchanged since it depends only on f . Posterior means now read

$$\langle g \rangle_t := \frac{1}{Z_t} \int D\mathbf{a} D\mathbf{W} D\mathbf{v} D\xi \exp\left[\sum_{\mu=1}^n u_{Y_{t\mu}}(s_{t\mu})\right] g \quad (42)$$

for any observable g depending on $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{W}, \mathbf{v}, \xi$, where

$$Z_t = \int D\mathbf{a} D\mathbf{W} D\mathbf{v} D\xi \exp\left[\sum_{\mu=1}^n u_{Y_\mu}(s_{t\mu})\right]. \quad (43)$$

In the following we drop the subscript t to keep the notation light and simply use $\langle \cdot \rangle$. We also introduce the compact notation

$$\mathbb{E}_{(t)}(\cdot) := \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{a}^*} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{a}^*}(\cdot) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{a}^*} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*, \mathbf{v}^*, \xi^*, \{\mathbf{X}_\mu\}} \int \prod_{\mu=1}^n dY_{t\mu} e^{u_{Y_{t\mu}}(S_{t\mu})}(\cdot). \quad (44)$$

The free entropy of this interpolating model is thus

$$\bar{f}_n(t) := \frac{1}{n} \mathbb{E}_{(t)} \log Z_t, \quad (45)$$

whence it can be verified that

$$\bar{f}_n(0) = \bar{f}_n, \quad \bar{f}_n(1) = \bar{f}_n^\circ. \quad (46)$$

Due to the identity $\bar{f}_n(1) - \bar{f}_n(0) = \int_0^1 \frac{d}{dt} \bar{f}_n(t) dt$, a sufficient condition to prove our Theorem 2 is to show that $\frac{d}{dt} \bar{f}_n(t)$ is uniformly bounded by the same order as in the statement. A direct computation shows

$$\frac{d}{dt} \bar{f}_n(t) = -A_1 + A_2 + A_3 + B \quad (47)$$

where

$$A_1 := \frac{1}{2n} \mathbb{E}_{(t)} \log \mathcal{Z}_t \sum_{\mu=1}^n u'_{Y_{t\mu}}(S_{t\mu}) \frac{\mathbf{a}^{*\top}}{\sqrt{(1-t)p}} \varphi\left(\frac{\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}}\right), \quad (48)$$

$$A_2 := \frac{1}{2n} \mathbb{E}_{(t)} \log \mathcal{Z}_t \sum_{\mu=1}^n u'_{Y_{t\mu}}(S_{t\mu}) \rho \frac{\mathbf{v}^{*\top} \mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{td}}, \quad (49)$$

$$A_3 := \frac{1}{2n} \mathbb{E}_{(t)} \log \mathcal{Z}_t \sum_{\mu=1}^n u'_{Y_{t\mu}}(S_{t\mu}) \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon}{t}} \xi_\mu^*, \quad (50)$$

$$B := \frac{1}{n} \mathbb{E}_{(t)} \left\langle \sum_{\mu=1}^n u'_{Y_{t\mu}}(s_{t\mu}) \frac{ds_{t\mu}}{dt} \right\rangle. \quad (51)$$

We will control each term individually. For that we will need a number of Lemmas which we provide now.

3.2 Lemmata

We collect here some Lemmas that shall be used intensively in the following. For the convenience we postpone proofs to the Appendix.

Lemma 5 (Properties of P_{out}). *Recall the definition $u_y(x) := \log P_{\text{out}}(y | x)$. We denote $u'_y(x) := \partial_x u_y(x)$. Furthermore, let*

$$U_{\mu\nu} := \delta_{\mu\nu} u''_{Y_{t\mu}}(S_{t\mu}) + u'_{Y_{t\mu}}(S_{t\mu}) u'_{Y_{t\nu}}(S_{t\nu}). \quad (52)$$

Under Assumptions (H1) and (H2) the following statements hold:

$$\mathbb{E}[u'_{Y_{t\mu}}(S_{t\mu}) | S_{t\mu}] = \mathbb{E}[U_{\mu\nu} | S_{t\mu}, S_{t\nu}] = 0, \quad (53)$$

$$\mathbb{E}[(u'_{Y_{t\mu}}(S_{t\mu}))^2 | S_{t\mu}], \mathbb{E}[U_{\mu\nu}^2 | S_{t\mu}, S_{t\nu}] \leq C(f), \quad (54)$$

for a positive constant $C(f)$ depending solely on the readout function.

Remark 2. It is worth to point out a simple observation that for $\mu = \nu$ we have $U_{\mu\mu} = P''_{\text{out}}(Y_{t\mu} | S_{t\mu})/P_{\text{out}}(Y_{t\mu} | S_{t\mu})$, where

$$P'_{\text{out}}(y | x) := \partial_x P_{\text{out}}(y | x), \quad P''_{\text{out}}(y | x) := \partial_x \partial_x P_{\text{out}}(y | x),$$

from what immediately follows

$$\mathbb{E}\left[\left(\frac{P''_{\text{out}}(Y_{t\mu} | S_{t\mu})}{P_{\text{out}}(Y_{t\mu} | S_{t\mu})}\right)^2 \mid S_{t\mu}\right] \leq C(f). \quad (55)$$

The following lemma will play a crucial role, and it contains all the approximations due to the law of large numbers. We introduce here a convenient notation for the pre-activations:

$$\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu := \frac{\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}}. \quad (56)$$

Hence, conditionally on the inputs $(\mathbf{X}_\mu)_{\mu \leq n}$, the α 's have covariance

$$\frac{1}{p} \mathbb{E}[\alpha_\mu^\top \alpha_\nu \mid \mathbf{X}_\mu, \mathbf{X}_\nu] := \frac{1}{p} \mathbb{E} \mathbf{W}^* \frac{(\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{X}_\mu)^\top}{\sqrt{d}} \frac{\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{X}_\nu}{\sqrt{d}} = \frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{d}. \quad (57)$$

Lemma 6 (Approximations). *Let $\tilde{\varphi}$ be either φ or the identity function. Under assumptions (H1) and (H2) the following estimates hold for any choice of $\mu, \nu \leq n$:*

$$\mathbb{E} \mathbf{W}^* \varphi'(\alpha_{\mu i}) = \rho + O\left(\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_\mu\|^2}{d} - 1\right), \quad (58)$$

$$\mathbb{E} \mathbf{W}^* \varphi^2(\alpha_{\mu i}) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)} \varphi^2 + O\left(\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_\mu\|^2}{d} - 1\right), \quad (59)$$

$$\mathbb{E} \mathbf{W}^* \varphi(\alpha_{\mu i}) \tilde{\varphi}(\alpha_{\nu i}) = \rho \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)} \tilde{\varphi}' \frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{d} + O\left(\frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{d} \left(\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_\mu\|^2}{d} - 1\right)\right) + O\left(\left(\frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{\|\mathbf{X}_\nu\|^2}\right)^2\right) + O\left(\frac{(\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu)^2}{\|\mathbf{X}_\nu\|^2 d}\right), \quad (60)$$

$$\mathbb{E} \mathbf{W}^* \varphi'(\alpha_{\mu i}) \varphi'(\alpha_{\nu i}) = \rho^2 + O\left(\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_\mu\|^2}{d} - 1\right) + O\left(\frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{\|\mathbf{X}_\nu\|^2}\right), \quad (61)$$

$$\mathbb{E} \mathbf{W}^* \varphi^2(\alpha_{\mu i}) \tilde{\varphi}^2(\alpha_{\nu i}) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)} \varphi^2 \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)} \tilde{\varphi}^2 + O\left(\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_\mu\|^2}{d} - 1\right) + O\left(\frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{\|\mathbf{X}_\nu\|^2}\right). \quad (62)$$

The final key ingredient is the concentration of the free entropy, that we prove in Section 4.

Theorem 7 (Free entropy concentration). *Under assumptions (H1) and (H2) there exists a non-negative constant $C(f, \varphi)$ such that*

$$\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{a}^*} \mathbb{V}_{\mathbf{a}^*} \left(\frac{1}{n} \log \mathcal{Z}_t \right) = \mathbb{E} \left(\frac{1}{n} \log \mathcal{Z}_t - \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{a}^*} \frac{1}{n} \log \mathcal{Z}_t \right)^2 \leq C(f, \varphi) \left(\frac{1}{d} + \frac{1}{n} \right). \quad (63)$$

Remark 3. More detailed expression for constant $C(f, \varphi)$ is given in Appendix D.

3.3 Proof of Theorem 2

We split the proof of Theorem 2 into different Lemmas for the sake of readability. The proof of Lemma 6 is given in Appendix C. If not differently specified, all the following Lemmas hold under the same hypotheses of Theorem 2. The first one concerns the B contribution to the derivative of the free entropy (47).

Lemma 8 (B term). $B = 0$.

Proof. The random variable inside the brackets in (51) is a function of the data $Y_{t\mu}$ and of a sample from the posterior through $s_{t\mu}$. Hence we can use the Nishimori identities to get rid of the brackets, replacing $s_{t\mu}$ with the ground truth version $S_{t\mu}$ (from now on we denote with an upper dot $\dot{S} := \frac{dS}{dt}$ the t -derivative):

$$B = \frac{1}{n} \mathbb{E}_{(t)} \sum_{\mu=1}^n u'_{Y_{t\mu}}(S_{t\mu}) \dot{S}_{t\mu} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{\mu=1}^n \mathbb{E}_{(t)} \left[\mathbb{E}_{(t)} [u'_{Y_{t\mu}}(S_{t\mu}) \mid S_{t\mu}] \dot{S}_{t\mu} \right] \quad (64)$$

where we used the tower rule for expectations. The latter is identically zero thanks to Lemma 5. \square

We split A_1 into two other contributions $A_1 = A_{11} + A_{12}$ where

$$A_{11} := \frac{1}{2n\sqrt{1-t}} \mathbb{E}_{(t)} \log \mathcal{Z}_t \sum_{\mu=1}^n u'_{Y_{t\mu}}(S_{t\mu}) \left(\frac{\mathbf{a}^{*\top}}{\sqrt{p}} \varphi \left(\frac{\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}} \right) - \frac{\rho \mathbf{a}^{*\top} \mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{pd}} \right), \quad (65)$$

$$A_{12} := \frac{1}{2n\sqrt{1-t}} \mathbb{E}_{(t)} \log \mathcal{Z}_t \sum_{\mu=1}^n u'_{Y_{t\mu}}(S_{t\mu}) \frac{\rho \mathbf{a}^{*\top} \mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{pd}}. \quad (66)$$

Let us simplify these terms by Gaussian integration by parts. In A_{12} , integrating by parts w.r.t. \mathbf{W}^* yields

$$A_{12} = \frac{\rho}{2n} \mathbb{E}_{(t)} \log \mathcal{Z}_t \sum_{\mu, \nu=1}^n U_{\mu\nu} \frac{\mathbf{a}^{*\top} (\mathbf{a}^* \circ \varphi'(\frac{\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{X}_\nu}{\sqrt{d}})) \mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{p d} \quad (67)$$

with $U_{\mu\nu}$ defined in Lemma 5 and \circ denotes the entry-wise (Hadamard) product. Concerning A_{11} , because of the non-linearity, we can only integrate by parts w.r.t. \mathbf{a}^* and obtain

$$A_{11} = \frac{1}{2n} \mathbb{E}_{(t)} \log \mathcal{Z}_t \sum_{\mu, \nu=1}^n U_{\mu\nu} \left[\frac{\varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu)^\top \varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\nu) - \rho \boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu^\top \varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\nu)}{p} \right]. \quad (68)$$

The off-diagonal $\mu \neq \nu$ and diagonal terms in the previous equations play two very different roles, and they shall be treated separately in the following.

Lemma 9 (Off-diagonal part of A_{11}). *The following holds:*

$$A_{11}^{\text{off}} := \frac{1}{n} \mathbb{E}_{(t)} \log \mathcal{Z}_t \sum_{\mu \neq \nu} U_{\mu\nu} \left[\frac{\varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu)^\top \varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\nu) - \rho \boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu^\top \varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\nu)}{p} \right] = O\left(\sqrt{\left(1 + \frac{n}{d}\right) \left(\frac{n}{p} + \frac{n}{d^{3/2}}\right)}\right). \quad (69)$$

Proof. Let us start noticing that, for any smooth function $F(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu, \boldsymbol{\alpha}_\nu)$ we have

$$\mathbb{E}_{\setminus \mathbf{a}^*} U_{\mu\nu} F(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu, \boldsymbol{\alpha}_\nu) = \mathbb{E}_{\setminus \mathbf{a}^*} \left[\mathbb{E}_{\setminus \mathbf{a}^*} [U_{\mu\nu} \mid \mathbf{W}^*, \mathbf{v}^*, \boldsymbol{\xi}^*, \mathbf{X}] F(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu, \boldsymbol{\alpha}_\nu) \right] = 0 \quad (70)$$

thanks to Lemma 5. As a consequence, with \mathbf{a}^* fixed, we can modify A_{11}^{off} as follows without changing its value:

$$A_{11}^{\text{off}} = \mathbb{E}_{\setminus \mathbf{a}^*} (f_n - \mathbb{E}_{\setminus \mathbf{a}^*} f_n) \sum_{\mu \neq \nu} U_{\mu\nu} \left[\frac{\varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu)^\top \varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\nu) - \rho \boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu^\top \varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\nu)}{p} \right] \quad (71)$$

with $f_n := \log \mathcal{Z}_t / n$. In the following we shall simply write u'_μ in place of $u'_{Y_{t\mu}}(S_{t\mu})$, and φ_μ instead of $\varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu)$ for brevity. We are now in position to use Cauchy-Schwartz's identity:

$$(A_{11}^{\text{off}})^2 \leq \mathbb{V}_{\setminus \mathbf{a}^*} [f_n] \sum_{\mu \neq \nu} \sum_{\lambda \neq \eta} \mathbb{E}_{\setminus \mathbf{a}^*} U_{\mu\nu} U_{\lambda\eta} \left[\frac{\varphi_\mu^\top \varphi_\nu - \rho \boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu^\top \varphi_\nu}{p} \right] \left[\frac{\varphi_\lambda^\top \varphi_\eta - \rho \boldsymbol{\alpha}_\lambda^\top \varphi_\eta}{p} \right]. \quad (72)$$

Note that when all the four Greek indices are different from one another we get the highest combinatorial factor of $O(n^4)$. However, using the conditional independence of the responses and Lemma 5, the expectation sets them to 0. Hence, the only contributions from the double sums come from $\mu = \lambda$ and $\nu = \eta$, or $\mu = \eta$ and $\nu = \lambda$, which gives twice the same quantity. Thus

$$(A_{11}^{\text{off}})^2 \leq \mathbb{V}_{\setminus \mathbf{a}^*} [f_n] \frac{2}{p^2} \sum_{\mu \neq \nu} \mathbb{E}_{\setminus \mathbf{a}^*} (u'_\mu u'_\nu)^2 \sum_{i,j=1}^p [\varphi_{\mu i} \varphi_{\nu i} \varphi_{\mu j} \varphi_{\nu j} - 2\rho \alpha_{\mu i} \varphi_{\nu i} \varphi_{\mu j} \varphi_{\nu j} + \rho^2 \alpha_{\mu i} \varphi_{\nu i} \alpha_{\mu j} \varphi_{\nu j}]. \quad (73)$$

The double sum on i, j comes from the square of a scalar product. Lemma 5 then allows to bound $\mathbb{E}[U_{\mu\nu}^2 \mid S_{t\mu}, S_{t\nu}]$ by a constant.

Let us treat the off-diagonal terms ($i \neq j$) first. We call Lemma 6, in particular (60), to simplify the first term in (73):

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{a}^*} \sum_{i \neq j, 1}^p \varphi(\alpha_{\mu i}) \varphi(\alpha_{\nu i}) \varphi(\alpha_{\mu j}) \varphi(\alpha_{\nu j}) &= p(p-1) \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}_\mu, \mathbf{X}_\nu} (\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} [\varphi(\alpha_{\mu 1}) \varphi(\alpha_{\nu 1})])^2 \\
&= p(p-1) \mathbb{E} \left[\rho^4 \left(\frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{d} \right)^2 + O \left(\frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{d} \left(\frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{\|\mathbf{X}_\nu\|^2} \right)^2 \right) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + O \left(\left(\frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{d} \right)^2 \frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{\|\mathbf{X}_\nu\|^2} \right) + O \left(\left(\frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{d} \right)^2 \left(\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_\nu\|^2}{d} - 1 \right) \right) \right]. \tag{74}
\end{aligned}$$

The first term in the square brackets corresponds to the square of the leading term in (60) with $\tilde{\varphi} = \varphi$. The other two terms are obtained as cross products between the leading term in (60) and the remainders.

Exploiting the fact that the norm of a Gaussian vector concentrates with exponential speed, i.e.,

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\left| \frac{\|\mathbf{X}_\mu\|^2}{d} - 1 \right| \geq h \right) \leq \exp \left(- \frac{dLh^2}{2} \right), \quad L > 0, \forall h > 0, \tag{75}$$

one can conclude that

$$\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{a}^*} \sum_{i \neq j, 1}^p \varphi(\alpha_{\mu i}) \varphi(\alpha_{\nu i}) \varphi(\alpha_{\mu j}) \varphi(\alpha_{\nu j}) = p(p-1) \left[\frac{\rho^4}{d} + O \left(\frac{1}{d^{3/2}} \right) \right]. \tag{76}$$

We now turn to the second term of (73): using again a Gaussian integration by part for the second equality below followed by Lemma 6 we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\rho \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}_\mu, \mathbf{X}_\nu} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \sum_{i \neq j}^p \alpha_{\mu i} \varphi_{\nu i} \varphi_{\mu j} \varphi_{\nu j} &= \rho p(p-1) \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}_\mu, \mathbf{X}_\nu} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} [\alpha_{\mu 1} \varphi_{\nu 1}] \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} [\varphi_{\mu 1} \varphi_{\nu 1}] \\
&= \rho p(p-1) \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}_\mu, \mathbf{X}_\nu} \frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{d} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} [\varphi'_{\nu 1}] \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} [\varphi_{\mu 1} \varphi_{\nu 1}] \\
&= p(p-1) \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}_\mu, \mathbf{X}_\nu} \left[\rho^2 \frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{d} + O \left(\frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{d} \left(\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_\mu\|^2}{d} - 1 \right) \right) \right] \\
&\quad \times \left[\rho^2 \frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{d} + O \left(\left(\frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{\|\mathbf{X}_\nu\|^2} \right)^2 \right) + O \left(\frac{(\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu)^2}{\|\mathbf{X}_\nu\|^2 d} \right) + O \left(\frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{d} \left(\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_\mu\|^2}{d} - 1 \right) \right) \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{77}$$

which shows that

$$\rho \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}_\mu, \mathbf{X}_\nu} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \sum_{i \neq j}^p \alpha_{\mu i} \varphi_{\nu i} \varphi_{\mu j} \varphi_{\nu j} = p(p-1) \left[\frac{\rho^4}{d} + O \left(\frac{1}{d^{3/2}} \right) \right]. \tag{78}$$

Finally, for what concerns the off-diagonal terms $i \neq j$, we deal with the last term of (73):

$$\begin{aligned}
\rho^2 \sum_{i \neq j}^p \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}_\mu, \mathbf{X}_\nu} \alpha_{\mu i} \varphi_{\nu i} \alpha_{\mu j} \varphi_{\nu j} &= \rho^2 p(p-1) \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}_\mu, \mathbf{X}_\nu} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} [\alpha_{\mu 1} \varphi_{\nu 1}] \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} [\alpha_{\mu 1} \varphi_{\nu 1}] \\
&= p(p-1) \rho^2 \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}_\mu, \mathbf{X}_\nu} \left(\frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{d} \right)^2 \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi'_{\mu 1} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi'_{\nu 1} \\
&= p(p-1) \left[\frac{\rho^4}{d} + O \left(\frac{1}{d^{3/2}} \right) \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{79}$$

where we used integration by parts and the approximation Lemma 6. From this computation we see that, remarkably, the leading orders of the off-diagonal terms $i \neq j$ in (73) cancel each other, leaving the more

convenient rate $O(1/d^{3/2})$. More precisely, there exists an absolute constant K such that

$$(A_{11}^{\text{off}})^2 \leq \mathbb{V}_{\mathbf{a}^*}[f_n] \frac{2K}{p^2} \sum_{\mu \neq \nu} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{a}^*} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^p [\varphi_{\mu i}^2 \varphi_{\nu i}^2 - 2\rho \alpha_{\mu i} \varphi_{\nu i}^2 \varphi_{\mu i} + \rho^2 \alpha_{\mu i}^2 \varphi_{\nu i}^2] + O\left(\frac{p^2}{d^{3/2}}\right) \right\}. \quad (80)$$

From the previous bound we see that we cannot hope that the same cancellation occurs in the diagonal terms $i = j$. Using again the results from Lemma 6 one can show that

$$(A_{11}^{\text{off}})^2 \leq \mathbb{V}_{\mathbf{a}^*}[f_n] \frac{2K}{p^2} \sum_{\mu \neq \nu} \left[O(p) + O\left(\frac{p^2}{d^{3/2}}\right) \right]. \quad (81)$$

The statement is thus proved after we take care of the remaining expectation over \mathbf{a}^* using Theorem 7:

$$|\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{a}^*} A_{11}^{\text{off}}| \leq \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{a}^*} \sqrt{(A_{11}^{\text{off}})^2} \leq \sqrt{\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{a}^*} \mathbb{V}_{\mathbf{a}^*}[f_n] O\left(\frac{n^2}{p} + \frac{n^2}{d^{3/2}}\right)} = O\left(\sqrt{\frac{n}{p} + \frac{n}{d^{3/2}} + \frac{n^2}{dp} + \frac{n^2}{d^{5/2}}}\right). \quad (82)$$

□

Remark 4. The previous result is telling us that the number of data points n can grow as fast as $o(d^{3/2})$ with the size of the input layer, but has to be much smaller than p , the size of the hidden layer. Furthermore, treating the difference $\varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu)^\top \varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\nu) - \rho \boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu^\top \varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\nu)$ altogether is fundamental to obtain the scaling $n^2 d^{-3/2}$ instead of $n^2 d^{-1}$. We also stress that the pre-activations $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu$ in the hidden layer have correlations among them that scale as $d^{-1/2}$. If d is not big enough they cannot be considered weakly correlated.

From Lemma 9 we thus infer that

$$A_{11} = \frac{1}{2n} \mathbb{E}_{(t)} \log \mathcal{Z}_t \sum_{\mu=1}^n \frac{P''_{\text{out}}(Y_{t\mu} | S_{t\mu})}{P_{\text{out}}(Y_{t\mu} | S_{t\mu})} \left[\frac{\|\varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu)\|^2 - \rho \boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu^\top \varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu)}{p} \right] + O\left(\sqrt{\left(1 + \frac{n}{d}\right) \left(\frac{n}{p} + \frac{n}{d^{3/2}}\right)}\right). \quad (83)$$

For the term A_3 we use integration by parts with respect to the variables Gaussian ξ_μ^* :

$$A_3 = \frac{\epsilon}{2n} \mathbb{E}_{(t)} \log \mathcal{Z}_t \sum_{\mu=1}^n \left((u'_{Y_{t\mu}}(S_{t\mu}))^2 + u''_{Y_{t\mu}}(S_{t\mu}) \right) = \frac{\epsilon}{2d} \mathbb{E}_{(t)} \log \mathcal{Z}_t \sum_{\mu=1}^n \frac{P''_{\text{out}}(Y_{t\mu} | S_{t\mu})}{P_{\text{out}}(Y_{t\mu} | S_{t\mu})}. \quad (84)$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} & A_3 - A_{11} \\ &= \frac{1}{2n} \mathbb{E}_{(t)} \log \mathcal{Z}_t \sum_{\mu=1}^n \frac{P''_{\text{out}}(Y_{t\mu} | S_{t\mu})}{P_{\text{out}}(Y_{t\mu} | S_{t\mu})} \left[\epsilon - \frac{\|\varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu)\|^2 - \rho \boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu^\top \varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu)}{p} \right] + O\left(\sqrt{\left(1 + \frac{n}{d}\right) \left(\frac{n}{p} + \frac{n}{d^{3/2}}\right)}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (85)$$

Lemma 10 ($A_3 - A_{11}^{\text{diag}}$ term). *The following asymptotics holds:*

$$A_3 - A_{11}^{\text{diag}} := \frac{1}{2n} \mathbb{E}_{(t)} \log \mathcal{Z}_t \sum_{\mu=1}^n \frac{P''_{\text{out}}(Y_{t\mu} | S_{t\mu})}{P_{\text{out}}(Y_{t\mu} | S_{t\mu})} \left[\epsilon - \frac{\|\varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu)\|^2 - \rho \boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu^\top \varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu)}{p} \right] \quad (86)$$

$$= O\left(\sqrt{\left(\frac{n}{d} + 1\right) \left(\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{d}}\right)}\right). \quad (87)$$

Proof. Define

$$C := \frac{1}{n} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{a}^*} \log \mathcal{Z}_t \sum_{\mu=1}^n \frac{P''_{\text{out}}(Y_{t\mu} | S_{t\mu})}{P_{\text{out}}(Y_{t\mu} | S_{t\mu})} \left[\epsilon - \frac{\|\varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu)\|^2 - \rho \boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu^\top \varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu)}{p} \right]. \quad (88)$$

First, thanks to Lemma 5

$$\mathbb{E}_{\setminus \mathbf{a}^*} \left[\frac{P''_{\text{out}}(Y_{t\mu} | S_{t\mu})}{P_{\text{out}}(Y_{t\mu} | S_{t\mu})} \mid \mathbf{W}^*, \mathbf{v}^*, \mathbf{X}_\mu, \xi_\mu^* \right] = 0, \quad (89)$$

and this allows us to center the $f_n = \log \mathcal{Z}_t/n$ with its mean without changing the value of C . After using Cauchy-Schwartz we have

$$\begin{aligned} C^2 &\leq \mathbb{V}_{\setminus \mathbf{a}^*} [f_n] \sum_{\mu, \nu=1}^n \mathbb{E}_{\setminus \mathbf{a}^*} \left[\mathbb{E}_{\setminus \mathbf{a}^*} \left[\frac{P''_{\text{out}}(Y_{t\mu} | S_{t\mu})}{P_{\text{out}}(Y_{t\mu} | S_{t\mu})} \frac{P''_{\text{out}}(Y_{t\nu} | S_{t\nu})}{P_{\text{out}}(Y_{t\nu} | S_{t\nu})} \mid \mathbf{W}^*, \mathbf{v}^*, \mathbf{X}_\mu, \mathbf{X}_\nu, \xi_\mu^*, \xi_\nu^* \right] \right. \\ &\quad \left. \times \left(\epsilon - \frac{\|\varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu)\|^2 - \rho \boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu^\top \varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu)}{p} \right) \left(\epsilon - \frac{\|\varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\nu)\|^2 - \rho \boldsymbol{\alpha}_\nu^\top \varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\nu)}{p} \right) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (90)$$

Thanks to the observation in (89), only the diagonal terms $\mu = \nu$ will survive in the double sum on the r.h.s. of the previous inequality. Furthermore recall (55). Hence the bound on C^2 becomes

$$C^2 \leq \mathbb{V}_{\setminus \mathbf{a}^*} [f_n] C(f) n \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}_1, \mathbf{W}^*} \left(\epsilon - \frac{\|\varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_1)\|^2 - \rho \boldsymbol{\alpha}_1^\top \varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_1)}{p} \right)^2. \quad (91)$$

Following an integration by part and Lemma 6 we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \alpha_{1i} \varphi(\alpha_{1i}) &= \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi'(\alpha_{1i}) \frac{\|\mathbf{X}_1\|^2}{d} = \frac{\|\mathbf{X}_1\|^2}{d} \left(\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)} \varphi' + O\left(\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_1\|^2}{d} - 1\right) \right) \\ &= \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)} \varphi' + O\left(\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_1\|^2}{d} - 1\right). \end{aligned} \quad (92)$$

From this and the approximation Lemma it follows that (letting $\mathbb{E}^2(\dots) = (\mathbb{E}(\dots))^2$)

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}_1} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \left[\frac{\|\varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_1)\|^2 - \rho \boldsymbol{\alpha}_1^\top \varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_1)}{p} \right] &= \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)} \varphi^2 - \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)}^2 \varphi' + O\left(\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}_1} \left| \frac{\|\mathbf{X}_1\|^2}{d} - 1 \right| \right) \\ &= \epsilon + O(d^{-1/2}), \end{aligned} \quad (93)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}_1} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \left[\frac{\|\varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_1)\|^2 - \rho \boldsymbol{\alpha}_1^\top \varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_1)}{p} \right]^2 &= \frac{1}{p} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}_1} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} (\varphi^4(\alpha_{11}) - 2\rho \varphi^3(\alpha_{11}) \alpha_{11} + \rho^2 \alpha_{11}^2 \varphi^2(\alpha_{11})) \\ &\quad + \frac{p-1}{p} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}_1} (\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*}^2 \varphi^2(\alpha_{11}) - 2\rho \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi^2(\alpha_{11}) \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi(\alpha_{11}) \alpha_{11} + \rho^2 \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*}^2 \varphi(\alpha_{11}) \alpha_{11}) \\ &= \epsilon^2 + O(p^{-1}) + O(d^{-1/2}). \end{aligned} \quad (94)$$

Hence, we finally have

$$\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}_\mu, \mathbf{W}^*} \left(\epsilon - \frac{\|\varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu)\|^2 - \rho \boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu^\top \varphi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\mu)}{p} \right)^2 = O(p^{-1}) + O(d^{-1/2}). \quad (95)$$

Plugging this and the bound in Theorem 7 into the inequality for C^2 we readily get the statement. \square

Now the remaining goal is to prove that $A_2 - A_{12} \rightarrow 0$. Using integration by parts in A_2 w.r.t. \mathbf{v}^* we obtain

$$A_2 = \frac{\rho^2}{2n} \mathbb{E}_{(t)} \log \mathcal{Z}_t \sum_{\mu, \nu=1}^n U_{\mu\nu} \frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{d}. \quad (96)$$

Recall also formula (67) for A_{12} .

Lemma 11 ($A_{12} - A_2$ term). *The following asymptotics holds:*

$$A_{12} - A_2 = \frac{\rho}{2n} \mathbb{E}_{(t)} \log \mathcal{Z}_t \sum_{\mu, \nu=1}^n U_{\mu\nu} \frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{d} \left[\frac{\mathbf{a}^{*\top} (\mathbf{a}^* \circ \varphi'(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\nu))}{p} - \rho \right] = O\left(\sqrt{\left(1 + \frac{n}{d}\right) \left(\frac{n}{dp} + \frac{n}{d^{3/2}}\right)}\right). \quad (97)$$

Proof. Conditional on \mathbf{a}^* define

$$C := \frac{1}{n} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{a}^*} \log \mathcal{Z}_t \sum_{\mu, \nu=1}^n U_{\mu\nu} \frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{d} \left[\frac{\mathbf{a}^{*\top} (\mathbf{a}^* \circ \varphi'(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\nu))}{p} - \rho \right]. \quad (98)$$

As before, thanks to Lemma 5, we can center the random variable $\log \mathcal{Z}_t$ with its expectation $\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{a}^*} \log \mathcal{Z}_t$, without affecting C . We can thus use Cauchy-Schwartz's inequality, obtaining

$$C^2 \leq \mathbb{V}_{\mathbf{a}^*} [f_n] \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{a}^*} \sum_{\mu, \nu=1}^n \sum_{\lambda, \eta=1}^n U_{\mu\nu} U_{\lambda\eta} \frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{d} \left[\frac{\mathbf{a}^{*\top} (\mathbf{a}^* \circ \varphi'(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\nu))}{p} - \rho \right] \frac{\mathbf{X}_\lambda^\top \mathbf{X}_\eta}{d} \left[\frac{\mathbf{a}^{*\top} (\mathbf{a}^* \circ \varphi'(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\eta))}{p} - \rho \right] \quad (99)$$

for a given \mathbf{a}^* . Thanks again to Lemma 5 the only terms that survive in the above quadruple sum are those with $\mu = \nu = \lambda = \eta$, and $\mu \neq \nu$, $\lambda \neq \eta$ but with $\mu = \lambda$, $\nu = \eta$ or vice versa. Up to constants everything can be summed up as follows:

$$C^2 \leq K \mathbb{V}_{\mathbf{a}^*} [f_n] \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{a}^*} \sum_{\mu, \nu=1}^n \left(\frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{d} \right)^2 \left[\frac{\mathbf{a}^{*\top} (\mathbf{a}^* \circ \varphi'(\boldsymbol{\alpha}_\nu))}{p} - \rho \right]^2 \quad (100)$$

where we used again Lemma 5. Now, expanding the square and computing the \mathbf{W}^* average of φ' via Lemma 6 we readily get

$$C^2 \leq K' \mathbb{V}_{\mathbf{a}^*} [f_n] \sum_{\mu, \nu=1}^n \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}_\mu, \mathbf{X}_\nu} \left(\frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{d} \right)^2 \left[\left(\frac{\|\mathbf{a}^*\|^2}{p} - 1 \right)^2 + O\left(\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_\nu\|^2}{d} - 1 \right) \left(\frac{\|\mathbf{a}^*\|^4}{p^2} + \frac{\|\mathbf{a}^*\|^2}{p} \right) \right] \quad (101)$$

where K' is a suitable positive constant. Denoting the double sum by D we have

$$|A_2 - A_{12}| \leq K'' \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{a}^*} \sqrt{\mathbb{V}_{\mathbf{a}^*} [f_n]} \sqrt{D} \leq K'' \sqrt{\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{a}^*} \mathbb{V}_{\mathbf{a}^*} [f_n] \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{a}^*} D} = O\left(\sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{n} + \frac{1}{d}\right) \left(\frac{n^2}{dp} + \frac{n^2}{d^{3/2}}\right)}\right). \quad (102)$$

□

Putting the results of all the Lemmas in this section together we get that the t -derivative of the interpolating free entropy is bounded by

$$\frac{d}{dt} \bar{f}_n(t) = \underbrace{O\left(\sqrt{\left(1 + \frac{n}{d}\right) \left(\frac{n}{p} + \frac{n}{d^{3/2}}\right)}\right)}_{A_{11}^{\text{off}}} + \underbrace{O\left(\sqrt{\left(1 + \frac{n}{d}\right) \left(\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{d}}\right)}\right)}_{A_3 - A_{11}^{\text{diag}}} + \underbrace{O\left(\sqrt{\left(1 + \frac{n}{d}\right) \left(\frac{n}{dp} + \frac{n}{d^{3/2}}\right)}\right)}_{A_{12} - A_2} \quad (103)$$

$$= O\left(\sqrt{\left(1 + \frac{n}{d}\right) \left(\frac{n}{p} + \frac{n}{d^{3/2}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{d}}\right)}\right). \quad (104)$$

All the bounds in this section are uniform in $t \in [0, 1]$. This finishes the proof of Theorem 2.

4 Concentration of the free entropy

Here we prove that the free entropy of the interpolating model concentrates, i.e., Theorem 7. To simplify the notations we use $C(f, \varphi)$ for a generic non-negative constant depending only on f and φ . We recall

that the partition function is defined as

$$\mathcal{Z}_t = \int D\mathbf{a}D\mathbf{v}D\mathbf{W} \prod_{\mu=1}^n D\xi_{\mu} \exp \left[\sum_{\mu=1}^n \log P_{\text{out}}(Y_{t\mu}|s_{t\mu}) \right], \quad (105)$$

where

$$Y_{t\mu} = f(S_{t\mu}; \mathbf{A}_{\mu}) + \sqrt{\Delta}Z_{\mu}, \quad (106)$$

$$S_{t\mu} = \sqrt{1-t} \frac{\mathbf{a}^{*\top}}{\sqrt{p}} \varphi \left(\frac{\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{X}_{\mu}}{\sqrt{d}} \right) + \sqrt{t\rho} \frac{\mathbf{v}^{*\top} \mathbf{X}_{\mu}}{\sqrt{d}} + \sqrt{t\epsilon} \xi_{\mu}^*, \quad (107)$$

$$s_{t\mu} = \sqrt{1-t} \frac{\mathbf{a}^{\top}}{\sqrt{p}} \varphi \left(\frac{\mathbf{W} \mathbf{X}_{\mu}}{\sqrt{d}} \right) + \sqrt{t\rho} \frac{\mathbf{v}^{\top} \mathbf{X}_{\mu}}{\sqrt{d}} + \sqrt{t\epsilon} \xi_{\mu}. \quad (108)$$

We prove Theorem 7 in several steps, first we show concentration with respect only to $\{Z_{\mu}\}_{\mu}$, $\{\xi_{\mu}^*\}_{\mu}$ and $\{\mathbf{X}_{\mu}\}_{\mu}$ using classical Poincaré-Nash inequality, then with respect to $\{\mathbf{A}_{\mu}\}_{\mu}$ using the corollary of Efron-Stein inequality, and then finally with respect to \mathbf{W}^* with \mathbf{v}^* . For this we rewrite

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E} \left(\frac{1}{n} \log \mathcal{Z}_t - \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{v}^*, \mathbf{W}^*, \mathbf{X}, \xi^*, \mathbf{A}, \mathbf{Z}} \frac{1}{n} \log \mathcal{Z}_t \right)^2 &= \\ &= \mathbb{E} \left(\frac{1}{n} \log \mathcal{Z}_t - \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}, \xi^*, \mathbf{Z}} \frac{1}{n} \log \mathcal{Z}_t \right)^2 + \mathbb{E} \left(\frac{1}{n} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}, \xi^*, \mathbf{Z}} \log \mathcal{Z}_t - \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{A}} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}, \xi^*, \mathbf{Z}} \frac{1}{n} \log \mathcal{Z}_t \right)^2 + \\ &\quad + \mathbb{E} \left(\mathbb{E}_{\psi} \frac{1}{n} \log \mathcal{Z}_t - \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{v}^*, \mathbf{W}^*} \mathbb{E}_{\psi} \frac{1}{n} \log \mathcal{Z}_t \right)^2 \end{aligned} \quad (109)$$

where by \mathbb{E}_{ψ} we denoted the joint expectation with respect to \mathbf{Z} , ξ^* , \mathbf{X} , and \mathbf{A} . Also for brevity, in what follows, by writing \mathbf{Z} , ξ^* , \mathbf{X} , and \mathbf{A} we mean the sets $\{Z_{\mu}\}_{\mu}$, etc. We recall two classical concentration results, whose proofs can be found in [Boucheron et al. \(2004\)](#), Chapter 3.

Proposition 12 (Poincaré-Nash inequality). *Let $\xi = [\xi_1, \dots, \xi_K]^{\top}$ be a real Gaussian standard random vector. If $g : \mathbb{R}^K \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a continuously differentiable function, then*

$$\mathbb{V}g(\xi) \leq \mathbb{E} \|\nabla g(\xi)\|^2. \quad (110)$$

Proposition 13 (Bounded difference). *Let $\xi = [\xi_1, \dots, \xi_K]^{\top}$ be a random vector with i.i.d. elements taking values in some space \mathcal{A} . If function $g : \mathcal{A}^K \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ satisfies*

$$\sup_{1 \leq i \leq K} \sup_{x_1, \dots, x_K, x'_i \in \mathcal{A}} |g(x_1, \dots, x_i, \dots, x_K) - g(x_1, \dots, x'_i, \dots, x_K)| \leq C \quad (111)$$

for some $C > 0$, then

$$\mathbb{V}\{g(\xi)\} \leq \frac{1}{4} K C^2. \quad (112)$$

In what follows we will denote $P^y(y|x) := \frac{\partial P_{\text{out}}(y|x)}{\partial y}$ and $P^x(y|x) := \frac{\partial P_{\text{out}}(y|x)}{\partial x}$.

Lemma 14. *There exists a non-negative constant $C(f, \varphi)$ such that*

$$\mathbb{E} \left(\frac{1}{n} \log \mathcal{Z}_t - \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}, \xi^*, \mathbf{Z}} \frac{1}{n} \log \mathcal{Z}_t \right)^2 \leq \frac{C(f, \varphi)}{n}.$$

Proof. Since ξ_{μ}^* , Z_{μ} and all elements of vectors \mathbf{X}_{μ} are jointly independent for all μ , we have thanks to Proposition 12

$$\mathbb{E} \mathbb{V}_{\mathbf{X}, \xi^*, \mathbf{Z}} \left(\frac{1}{n} \log \mathcal{Z}_t \right) \leq \frac{1}{n^2} \mathbb{E} \|\nabla \log \mathcal{Z}_t\|^2$$

$$= \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{\mu=1}^n \mathbb{E} \left(\frac{\partial \log \mathcal{Z}_t}{\partial \xi_\mu^*} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{\mu=1}^n \sum_{i=1}^d \mathbb{E} \left(\frac{\partial \log \mathcal{Z}_t}{\partial X_\mu^i} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{\mu=1}^n \mathbb{E} \left(\frac{\partial \log \mathcal{Z}_t}{\partial Z_\mu} \right)^2 =: I_1 + I_2 + I_3.$$

For the sake of brevity we drop index out and write $P_\mu = P_{\text{out}}(Y_{t,\mu} | s_{t,\mu})$ in what follows. Gibbs brackets $\langle \cdot \rangle$ are defined as in (44). After taking derivative in the first term we obtain

$$\left| \frac{\partial \log \mathcal{Z}_t}{\partial \xi_\mu^*} \right| = \left| \left\langle \frac{P_\mu^y}{P_\mu} \right\rangle f'(S_{t,\mu}; \mathbf{A}_\mu) \sqrt{t\epsilon} \right| \leq \sqrt{t\epsilon} C(f) (|Z_\mu|^2 + 1).$$

Last inequality is due to boundedness of f' and Lemma 18. One can see that the only randomness left is in Z_μ . Since it is Gaussian, the average of polynomial is bounded by some uniform constant c . We obtained that each term in I_1 is bounded by constant, the number of terms is n , from this it follows immediately that $I_1 \leq C(f)/n$.

The second type of partial derivative will give us

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \log \mathcal{Z}_t}{\partial X_\mu^i} &= \left\langle \frac{P_\mu^y}{P_\mu} \right\rangle f'(S_{t,\mu}; \mathbf{A}_\mu) \left(\sqrt{1-t} \frac{(\mathbf{a}^* \circ \varphi'(\frac{\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{x}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}}) \mathbf{W}^*)_i}{\sqrt{pd}} + \sqrt{t\rho} \frac{v_i^*}{\sqrt{d}} \right) \\ &\quad + \left\langle \frac{P_\mu^x}{P_\mu} \frac{(\mathbf{a} \circ \varphi'(\frac{\mathbf{W} \mathbf{x}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}}) \mathbf{W})_i}{\sqrt{pd}} \right\rangle \sqrt{1-t} + \left\langle \frac{P_\mu^x}{P_\mu} \frac{v_i}{\sqrt{d}} \right\rangle \sqrt{t\rho}. \end{aligned}$$

Plugging this into I_2 and using the simple inequality $\mathbb{E}(a+b)^2 \leq 2(\mathbb{E}a^2 + \mathbb{E}b^2)$ in order to square each term of the r.h.s. separately, we notice that the following terms appear

$$\mathbb{E} \left\langle \frac{P_\mu^x}{P_\mu} \frac{(\mathbf{a} \circ \varphi'(\frac{\mathbf{W} \mathbf{x}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}}) \mathbf{W})_i}{\sqrt{pd}} \right\rangle^2, \quad \mathbb{E} \left\langle \frac{P_\mu^x}{P_\mu} \frac{v_i}{\sqrt{d}} \right\rangle^2,$$

which depend only on $Y_{t,\mu}, S_{t,\mu}$ and $s_{t,\mu}$. This allow us to use Nishimori identity by removing the brackets and adding $*$ to \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{W} and \mathbf{v} . Then evaluating each ratio with P_{out} using Lemma 18 we get

$$I_2 \leq \frac{C(f)(1-t)}{n^2} \sum_{\mu=1}^n \mathbb{E} \left((|Z_\mu|^2 + 1)^2 \frac{\|\mathbf{a}^* \circ \varphi'(\frac{\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{x}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}}) \mathbf{W}^*\|^2}{pd} \right) + \frac{C(f)t\rho}{n} \mathbb{E} \left((|Z_\mu|^2 + 1)^2 \frac{\|\mathbf{v}^*\|^2}{d} \right). \quad (113)$$

after what we notice that factors $(|Z_\mu|^2 + 1)^2$ are independent of others and its expectation can be bounded with positive constant. In the end we obtain

$$I_2 \leq \frac{C(f)}{n^2} \sum_{\mu=1}^n \mathbb{E} \frac{\|\mathbf{a}^* \circ \varphi'(\frac{\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{x}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}}) \mathbf{W}^*\|^2}{pd} + \frac{C(f)}{n}. \quad (114)$$

To finish the proof we notice that when we expand the norm appearing above, only even moments survive, e.g., $\mathbb{E}(a_i^* \varphi'_i W_{ij}^*)^2$, and so each term is positive. This gives as opportunity to bound φ' with $C(\varphi)$ in each term and calculate its expectation which is simply $C(\varphi)$. The number of such terms is exactly pd , this gives us simple bound $I_2 \leq C(f, \varphi)/n$.

Finally, the derivatives with respect to Z_μ are of the form

$$\frac{\partial \log \mathcal{Z}_t}{\partial Z_\mu} = \sqrt{\Delta} \left\langle \frac{P_\mu^y}{P_\mu} \right\rangle. \quad (115)$$

Similarly to what done above we bound I_3 with the help of Lemma 18

$$I_3 \leq \frac{C(f)}{n}. \quad (116)$$

□

Next step would be to prove the concentration of function $\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Z}, \xi^*} \log \mathcal{Z}_t/n$ with respect to \mathbf{A} using Proposition 13 while keeping \mathbf{W}^* and \mathbf{v}^* fixed.

Lemma 15. *There exists a constant $C(f, \varphi) > 0$ such that*

$$\mathbb{E} \left(\frac{1}{n} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Z}, \xi^*} \log \mathcal{Z}_t - \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{A}} \frac{1}{n} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Z}, \xi^*} \log \mathcal{Z}_t \right)^2 \leq \frac{C(f, \varphi)}{n}. \quad (117)$$

Proof. We consider $h(\mathbf{A}) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Z}, \xi^*} \log \mathcal{Z}_t/n$ a function of all the elements $\mathbf{A}_{\mu, i}$ of \mathbf{A}_μ for $1 \leq i \leq k$ and $1 \leq \mu \leq n$. We denote by \mathbf{A}' a vector such that $\mathbf{A}'_{\mu, i} = \mathbf{A}_{\mu, i}$ for $\mu \neq \nu, i \neq j$ and $\mathbf{A}'_{\nu, j}$ is a random variable with distribution P_A , independent of all others. According to Proposition 13 it is sufficient to prove that

$$|h(\mathbf{A}') - h(\mathbf{A})| < \frac{C(f, \varphi)}{n}. \quad (118)$$

If we denote by H (and H') the Hamiltonian corresponding to \mathcal{Z}_t (and \mathcal{Z}_t with \mathbf{A}') one can see that

$$h(\mathbf{A}') - h(\mathbf{A}) = \frac{1}{n} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Z}, \xi^*} \log \left\langle e^{H-H'} \right\rangle_H \geq \frac{1}{n} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Z}, \xi^*} \left\langle H - H' \right\rangle_H, \quad (119)$$

the last step being true due to Jensen inequality. On the other hand $h(\mathbf{A}') - h(\mathbf{A}) \leq \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Z}, \xi^*} \langle H - H' \rangle_{H'}/n$. We recall the definition (2) of $P_{\text{out}}(Y_{t\mu}, s_{t\mu})$ and similarly we obtain

$$H - H' \geq \frac{1}{2\Delta} \left\langle (f(S_{t\nu}; \mathbf{A}_\nu) - f(s_{t\nu}; \tilde{\mathbf{A}}) + \sqrt{\Delta} Z_\nu)^2 - (f(S_{t\nu}; \mathbf{A}'_\nu) - f(s_{t\nu}; \tilde{\mathbf{A}}) + \sqrt{\Delta} Z_\nu)^2 \right\rangle_G \quad (120)$$

and

$$H - H' \leq \frac{1}{2\Delta} \left\langle (f(S_{t\nu}; \mathbf{A}_\nu) - f(s_{t\nu}; \tilde{\mathbf{A}}) + \sqrt{\Delta} Z_\nu)^2 - (f(S_{t\nu}; \mathbf{A}'_\nu) - f(s_{t\nu}; \tilde{\mathbf{A}}) + \sqrt{\Delta} Z_\nu)^2 \right\rangle_{G'}, \quad (121)$$

where $\langle \cdot \rangle_G$ (or with G') defined as

$$\langle \cdot \rangle_G = \frac{\int P_A(d\tilde{\mathbf{A}}) e^{-\frac{1}{2\Delta} (Y_{t\nu} - f(s_{t\nu}; \tilde{\mathbf{A}}))^2} (\cdot)}{\int P_A(d\tilde{\mathbf{A}}) e^{-\frac{1}{2\Delta} (Y_{t\nu} - f(s_{t\nu}; \tilde{\mathbf{A}}))^2}} \quad (122)$$

or with $Y'_{t\nu}$ where \mathbf{A}_ν is changed to \mathbf{A}'_ν . Since f is bounded we immediately obtain $|H - H'| \leq C(f)(|Z_\mu|^2 + 1)$ and (118). Now, due to the Proposition 13, the statement of the Lemma is proved. \square

The last part is to prove the concentration of function $g = \mathbb{E}_\psi \log \mathcal{Z}_t/n$ with respect to $\mathbf{W}^*, \mathbf{v}^*$.

Lemma 16. *There exists a constant $C(f, \varphi) > 0$ such that*

$$\mathbb{E}(g - \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*, \mathbf{v}^*} g)^2 \leq \frac{C(f, \varphi)}{d}. \quad (123)$$

Proof. Due to Poincaré-Nash inequality we have

$$\mathbb{E}(g - \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*, \mathbf{v}^*} g)^2 \leq \sum_{i,j}^{p,d} \mathbb{E} \left(\frac{\partial g}{\partial W_{ij}^*} \right)^2 + \sum_i^d \mathbb{E} \left(\frac{\partial g}{\partial v_i^*} \right)^2. \quad (124)$$

Let us first deal with the partial derivatives with respect to W_{ij}^*

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial W_{ij}^*} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_\mu^n \mathbb{E}_\psi \left(\left\langle \frac{P_\mu^y}{P_\mu} \right\rangle f'(S_{t\mu}, \mathbf{A}_\mu) \frac{\sqrt{1 - ta_i^* \varphi_i' X_\mu^j}}{\sqrt{pd}} \right), \quad (125)$$

where $\varphi'_i = \varphi'(\mathbf{W}_i^* \mathbf{X}_\mu / \sqrt{d})$. Before integrating by parts with respect to X_μ^j let us notice that in the sum over μ all terms are the same since we are taking the expectation over all i.i.d. vectors \mathbf{X}_μ , \mathbf{A}_μ , Z_μ and ξ_μ , it means that we can disregard the sum and just multiply by n directly. Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial g}{\partial W_{ij}^*} &= \mathbb{E}_\psi \left[\frac{\partial S_{t\mu}}{\partial X_\mu^j} \frac{\sqrt{1-t} a_i^* \varphi'_i}{\sqrt{pd}} \left(-\left\langle \frac{P_\mu^y}{P_\mu} \right\rangle^2 f'(S_{t\mu}; \mathbf{A}_\mu)^2 + \left\langle \frac{P_\mu^{yy}}{P_\mu} \right\rangle f'(S_{t\mu}; \mathbf{A}_\mu)^2 + \left\langle \frac{P_\mu^y}{P_\mu} \right\rangle f''(S_{t\mu}; \mathbf{A}_\mu) \right) \right] \\ &+ \mathbb{E}_\psi \left[\frac{\sqrt{1-t} a_i^* \varphi'_i}{\sqrt{pd}} \left(-\left\langle \frac{P_\mu^y}{P_\mu} \right\rangle \left\langle \frac{P_\mu^x}{P_\mu} \frac{\partial S_{t\mu}}{\partial X_\mu^j} \right\rangle + \left\langle \frac{P_\mu^{yx}}{P_\mu} \frac{\partial S_{t\mu}}{\partial X_\mu^j} \right\rangle \right) f'(S_{t\mu}; \mathbf{A}_\mu) \right] + \mathbb{E}_\psi \left[\frac{\sqrt{1-t} a_i^* \varphi''_i W_{ij}^*}{\sqrt{pd}} f'(S_{t\mu}; \mathbf{A}_\mu) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Due to the Lemma 18 absolute values of ratios of P 's are bounded with $C(f)(|Z_\mu|^2 + 1)$. In the first term of the expression above one can easily get rid of Z_μ since $\mathbb{E}_\psi \langle (1 + |Z_\mu|^2) \rangle < C$. On the other hand derivatives of f and φ , in view of (H2), remain bounded with non-negative constant $C(f, \varphi)$, so combining all above and plugging into latter expression along with derivatives of $S_{t\mu}$ and $s_{t\mu}$ we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \frac{\partial g}{\partial W_{ij}^*} \right| &\leq \frac{C(f, \varphi)}{\sqrt{d}} \mathbb{E}_\psi \left| \frac{(\mathbf{a}^* \circ \varphi'(\frac{\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}}) \mathbf{W}^*)_j}{\sqrt{pd}} \frac{a_i^*}{\sqrt{p}} \right| + \frac{C(f, \varphi)}{\sqrt{d}} \mathbb{E}_\psi \left| \frac{v_j^*}{\sqrt{d}} \frac{a_i^*}{\sqrt{p}} \right| \\ &\quad + \frac{C(f, \varphi)}{\sqrt{d}} \mathbb{E}_\psi \left| (|Z_\mu|^2 + 1) \frac{a_i^*}{\sqrt{p}} \left\langle \frac{(\mathbf{a} \circ \varphi'(\frac{\mathbf{W} \mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}}) \mathbf{W})_j}{\sqrt{pd}} \right\rangle \right| \\ &\quad + \frac{C(f, \varphi)}{\sqrt{d}} \mathbb{E}_\psi \left| (|Z_\mu|^2 + 1) \frac{a_i^*}{\sqrt{p}} \left\langle \frac{v_j}{\sqrt{d}} \right\rangle \right| + \frac{C(f, \varphi)}{\sqrt{d}} \mathbb{E}_\psi \left| \frac{a_i^* W_{ij}^*}{\sqrt{pd}} \right|. \end{aligned} \quad (126)$$

After using repeatedly $\mathbb{E}(a + b)^2 \leq 2\mathbb{E}a^2 + 2\mathbb{E}b^2$ along with Jensen inequality one can show

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i,j}^{p,d} \mathbb{E} \left| \frac{\partial g}{\partial W_{ij}^*} \right|^2 &\leq \frac{C(f, \varphi)}{d} \left(\mathbb{E} \left[\frac{\|\mathbf{a}^* \circ \varphi'(\frac{\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}}) \mathbf{W}^*\|^2}{pd} \frac{\|\mathbf{a}^*\|^2}{p} \right] \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{(|Z_\mu|^2 + 1)^2 \|\mathbf{a}^*\|^2}{p} \left\langle \frac{\|\mathbf{a} \circ \varphi'(\frac{\mathbf{W} \mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}}) \mathbf{W}\|^2}{pd} \right\rangle \right] + \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{(|Z_\mu|^2 + 1)^2 \|\mathbf{a}^*\|^2}{p} \left\langle \frac{\|\mathbf{v}\|^2}{d} \right\rangle \right] + 2 \right). \end{aligned} \quad (127)$$

Two terms of the form $\mathbb{E}[b\langle c \rangle]$ we bound by using Cauchy-Schwartz inequality, Jensen's inequality and Nishimori identity consecutively:

$$\mathbb{E}[b\langle c \rangle] \leq \mathbb{E}^{1/2}[b^2] \mathbb{E}^{1/2}[\langle c \rangle^2] \leq \mathbb{E}^{1/2}[b^2] \mathbb{E}^{1/2}[\langle c^2 \rangle] \leq \mathbb{E}^{1/2}[b^2] \mathbb{E}^{1/2}[c^2]. \quad (128)$$

This allows us to rewrite (127) as

$$\sum_{i,j}^{p,d} \mathbb{E} \left| \frac{\partial g}{\partial W_{ij}^*} \right|^2 \leq \frac{C(f, \varphi)}{d} \left(\mathbb{E}^{1/2} \left[\frac{\|\mathbf{a}^* \circ \varphi'(\frac{\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}}) \mathbf{W}^*\|^4}{p^2 d^2} \right] + C \right). \quad (129)$$

What is left is to notice that in $\mathbb{E} \|\mathbf{a}^* \circ \varphi'(\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{X}_\mu / \sqrt{d}) \mathbf{W}^*\|^4 / (p^2 d^2)$ all non zero terms will have only even powers so we can bound φ' with a constant in all of them, which gives immediately

$$\sum_{i,j}^{p,d} \mathbb{E} \left| \frac{\partial g}{\partial W_{ij}^*} \right|^2 \leq \frac{C(f, \varphi)}{d}. \quad (130)$$

Now we consider the partial derivative with respect to v_i^*

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial v_i^*} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{\mu} \mathbb{E}_\psi \left[\left\langle \frac{P_\mu^y}{P_\mu} \right\rangle f'(S_{t\mu}; \mathbf{A}_\mu) \frac{\sqrt{t} \rho X_\mu^i}{\sqrt{d}} \right]. \quad (131)$$

As in the case with W_{ij}^* it is necessary to integrate by parts also with respect to X_μ^i since blind bounds will not give us the desired order. The result will be very similar to the previous calculation just this time we don't have factors φ'_i and a_i^* . After similar simplification (bounds on ratios of P 's, etc.) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \frac{\partial g}{\partial v_i^*} \right| &\leq \frac{C(f, \varphi)}{\sqrt{d}} \mathbb{E}_\psi \left| \frac{(\mathbf{a}^* \circ \varphi'(\frac{\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}}) \mathbf{W}^*)_i}{\sqrt{pd}} \right| + \frac{C(f, \varphi)}{\sqrt{d}} \mathbb{E}_\psi \left| \frac{v_i^*}{\sqrt{d}} \right| \\ &\quad + \frac{C(f, \varphi)}{\sqrt{d}} \mathbb{E}_\psi \left[(|Z_\mu|^2 + 1) \left\langle \frac{(\mathbf{a} \circ \varphi'(\frac{\mathbf{W} \mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}}) \mathbf{W})_i}{\sqrt{pd}} \right\rangle \right] + \frac{C(f, \varphi)}{\sqrt{d}} \mathbb{E}_\psi \left[(|Z_\mu|^2 + 1) \left\langle \frac{v_i}{\sqrt{d}} \right\rangle \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (132)$$

Similarly to the previous case it is easy to see that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_i^d \mathbb{E} \left| \frac{\partial g}{\partial v_i^*} \right|^2 &\leq \frac{C(f, \varphi)}{d} \left(\mathbb{E} \left[\frac{\|\mathbf{a}^* \circ \varphi'(\frac{\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}}) \mathbf{W}^*\|^2}{pd} \right] + \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{\|\mathbf{v}^*\|^2}{d} \right] \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \mathbb{E} \left[(|Z_\mu|^2 + 1)^2 \left\langle \frac{\|\mathbf{a} \circ \varphi'(\frac{\mathbf{W} \mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}}) \mathbf{W}\|^2}{pd} \right\rangle \right] + \mathbb{E} \left[(|Z_\mu|^2 + 1)^2 \left\langle \frac{\|\mathbf{v}\|^2}{d} \right\rangle \right] \right). \end{aligned} \quad (133)$$

In order to be able to apply Nishimori identity to the last two terms we have first to use Cauchy-Schwarz inequality to separate factors with noise Z_μ from the Gibbs bracket. Due to the fact that φ' is bounded we obtain

$$\sum_i^d \mathbb{E} \left| \frac{\partial g}{\partial v_i^*} \right|^2 \leq \frac{C(f, \varphi)}{d}. \quad (134)$$

This combined with (130) finishes the proof. \square

5 Proof of Theorem 4

The proof is implied by that of Theorem 2. We introduce a further set of data $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_n := \{(\mathbf{X}_\nu, \tilde{Y}_\nu)\}_{n+1 \leq \nu \leq n(1+\eta)}$ with responses

$$\tilde{Y}_\nu = \sqrt{\lambda} Y'_\nu + \tilde{Z}'_\nu, \quad Y'_\nu \sim P_{\text{out}}(\cdot | S_\nu) \quad (135)$$

where $\lambda \geq 0$ and $n+1 \leq \nu \leq n(1+\eta)$ for some $\eta \geq 0$, \tilde{Z}'_ν are i.i.d. Gaussian variables independent of everything else, and where S_ν is defined as in (7) but for the new inputs, with same teacher as used to generate \mathcal{D}_n . We now define a proxy for the Bayes-optimal generalization error given the original and new data:

$$\mathcal{E}_n(\lambda, \eta) := \frac{1}{n\eta} \sum_{\nu=n+1}^{n(1+\eta)} \mathbb{E}[(Y'_\nu - \mathbb{E}[Y'_\nu | \mathcal{D}_n \cup \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_n])^2]. \quad (136)$$

This would recover the true definition of generalization if we set $\lambda = 0$ in it. The quantity $\mathcal{E}_n(\lambda, \eta)$ can be obtained through the I-MMSE relation Guo et al. (2005)

$$\frac{1}{n} \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda} I_n(\mathbf{Y}'; \sqrt{\lambda} \mathbf{Y}' + \mathbf{Z}' | \mathbf{Y}, (\mathbf{X}_\mu)_{\mu \leq n(1+\eta)}) = \frac{\eta}{2} \mathcal{E}_n(\lambda, \eta). \quad (137)$$

Following the general arguments in Barbier et al. (2019), the mutual information on the l.h.s. is concave in λ . Moreover the proof of Theorem 2 can be readily extended to take into account the additional side information (135): indeed, the proof is exactly the same as before except that the ‘‘channel’’ (135) generating the $n\eta$ responses is slightly different than the original one P_{out} . The new channel is equivalent to the original one once we rescale the readout f by $\sqrt{\lambda}f$ and the noise variance Δ as $\lambda\Delta + 1$ in (1). This

channel still verifies the same hypotheses. One then just need to keep track of the indices with responses generated according to the basic model (1) and those from the rescaled channel (135). In particular, it is possible to show the asymptotic equivalence of the quantities $I_n(\mathbf{Y}'; \sqrt{\lambda}\mathbf{Y}' + \mathbf{Z}' | \mathbf{Y}, (\mathbf{X}_\mu)_{\mu \leq n(1+\eta)})/n$ and $I_n^\circ(\mathbf{Y}'; \sqrt{\lambda}\mathbf{Y}' + \mathbf{Z}' | \mathbf{Y}, (\mathbf{X}_\mu)_{\mu \leq n(1+\eta)})/n$, where the second one refers to the equivalent GLM, with $S_\nu^\circ = \rho \mathbf{v}^{*\top} \mathbf{X}_\nu / \sqrt{d} + \sqrt{\epsilon} \xi_\nu^*$. Then by concavity one can use Griffiths' Lemma (see for instance (Ellis, 2006, Lemma IV.6.3)) to exchange the derivative with the limit $n \rightarrow \infty$ almost everywhere:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda} I_n(\mathbf{Y}'; \sqrt{\lambda}\mathbf{Y}' + \mathbf{Z}' | \mathbf{Y}, (\mathbf{X}_\mu)_{\mu \leq n(1+\eta)}) = \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} I_n^\circ(\mathbf{Y}'; \sqrt{\lambda}\mathbf{Y}' + \mathbf{Z}' | \mathbf{Y}, (\mathbf{X}_\mu)_{\mu \leq n(1+\eta)}). \quad (138)$$

The exchange fails when the model on the r.h.s., i.e. the GLM, presents a phase transition. Then one has to send both $\lambda, \eta \rightarrow 0$. The authors of Barbier et al. (2019) showed that these limits commute with the $n \rightarrow \infty$ limit for the GLM. So the r.h.s. yields the optimal generalization error for the GLM proved in Barbier et al. (2019) that is therefore shared by the Bayesian two-layer neural network under study.

6 Conclusions and perspectives

In this paper we provide a first step towards the proof of the Bayes-optimal limits for learning neural network target functions in an over-parameterized regime, namely when the number of parameters to be learn is much bigger than the number of training samples at disposal. Our result notably covers the case $n = O(d)$, which is the non-trivial scaling required for \mathcal{E}_n° to be asymptotically non trivial, as long as $p \gg d, n$. This asymmetry in the required scalings for the equivalence marks a difference with the conjecture of Cui et al. (2023), which instead allows for n, p, d to diverge proportionally to one another. This paper, however, laid the basis to remove this asymmetry, thus yielding to a fully rigorous proof of the conjecture in Camilli et al. (2025).

An attracting perspective is that of extending our analysis to data with more structure, starting for instance with \mathbf{X}_μ 's *i.i.d.* from a Gaussian with general covariance, and then with generic Gaussian mixtures (along the lines of Dandi et al. (2023) for GLMs), that, as it is known, can work as universal approximators Alspach and Sorenson (1972).

Finally, we stress that our analysis holds in the Bayes-optimal setting. Studying the problem in a different setting, e.g. with mismatching priors on the network weights, could require a completely different approach, and probably much more involved than the one employed here. Indeed, whereas Bayes-optimality gives guarantees on the replica symmetry (i.e., concentration-of-measure) of the model under rather mild assumptions Barbier and Panchenko (2022), a mismatched setting can give rise to replica symmetry breaking Mézard et al. (1987). Nevertheless, GEPs have successfully been used in mismatched estimation or for machines trained with empirical risk minimization, see e.g. Gerace et al. (2020); Hu and Lu (2022) (even if they deal with random features), which stands in favor of their validity in more general settings. This direction is worth of future investigation.

Appendix A Nishimori identity

The Nishimori identities are a very general set of symmetries arising in inference in the Bayes-optimal setting as a consequence of Bayes rule. They were initially discovered in the context of the gauge theory of spin glasses Nishimori (2001), which possess a sub-region of their phase space, called *Nishimori line*, where the most relevant thermodynamic quantities can be exactly computed, and we can generally count on replica symmetry, namely the concentration of order parameters Barbier and Panchenko (2022).

To introduce them, consider a generic inference problem where a Bayes-optimal statistician observes \mathbf{Y} that is a random function of some ground truth signal \mathbf{X}^* : $\mathbf{Y} \sim P_{Y|X}(\mathbf{X}^*)$. Then the following holds: **Proposition 17** (Nishimori identity). *For any bounded function f of the signal \mathbf{X}^* , the data \mathbf{Y} and of conditionally *i.i.d.* samples from the posterior $\mathbf{x}^j \sim P_{X|Y}(\cdot | \mathbf{Y})$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$, we have that*

$$\mathbb{E}\langle f(\mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{X}^*, \mathbf{x}^2, \dots, \mathbf{x}^n) \rangle = \mathbb{E}\langle f(\mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{x}^1, \mathbf{x}^2, \dots, \mathbf{x}^n) \rangle \quad (A1)$$

where the bracket notation $\langle \cdot \rangle$ is used for the joint expectation over the posterior samples $(\mathbf{x}^j)_{j \leq n}$, \mathbb{E} is over the signal \mathbf{X}^* and data \mathbf{Y} .

Proof. The proof follows directly from Bayes' rule. An elementary proof can be found in [Lelarge and Miolane \(2017\)](#). \square

Appendix B Proof of Lemma 5

Let us start with proving the auxiliary Lemma where we combine all necessary bounds concerning derivatives of $P_{\text{out}}(y|x)$. In what below $C(f)$ is a general constant that depends on f and also might depend on Δ . Below, upper indices represent partial derivatives, e.g., $P_{\text{out}}^x(y|x) = \partial_x P_{\text{out}}(y|x)$ and $P_{\text{out}}^{xx}(y|x) = \partial_x \partial_x P_{\text{out}}(y|x)$.

Lemma 18. *Let $y = Y_{t\mu} = f(S_{t\mu}; \mathbf{A}_\mu) + \sqrt{\Delta}Z_\mu$. Under assumption (H2) there exists constant $C(f)$ such that*

$$\max \left\{ \left| \frac{P_{\text{out}}^y(y|x)}{P_{\text{out}}(y|x)} \right|, \left| \frac{P_{\text{out}}^x(y|x)}{P_{\text{out}}(y|x)} \right|, \left| \frac{P_{\text{out}}^{yy}(y|x)}{P_{\text{out}}(y|x)} \right|, \left| \frac{P_{\text{out}}^{yx}(y|x)}{P_{\text{out}}(y|x)} \right|, \left| \frac{P_{\text{out}}^{xx}(y|x)}{P_{\text{out}}(y|x)} \right| \right\} < C(f)(|Z_\mu|^2 + 1). \quad (\text{B2})$$

Proof. For convenience we recall here the definition of $P_{\text{out}}(y|x)$

$$P_{\text{out}}(y|x) = \int dP_A(\mathbf{A}) \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\Delta}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2\Delta}(y - f(x; \mathbf{A}))^2\right). \quad (\text{B3})$$

It is easy to see that the ratio of any of these derivatives of P_{out} with P_{out} can be rewritten using an average

$$\langle \cdot \rangle_{\mathbf{A}} := \frac{\int dP_A(\mathbf{A}) (\cdot) e^{-\frac{1}{2\Delta}(y - f(x; \mathbf{A}))^2}}{\int dP_A(\mathbf{A}) e^{-\frac{1}{2\Delta}(y - f(x; \mathbf{A}))^2}}. \quad (\text{B4})$$

After some algebra we get

$$\frac{P_{\text{out}}^y(y|x)}{P_{\text{out}}(y|x)} = \left\langle -\frac{1}{\Delta}(y - f(x; \mathbf{A})) \right\rangle_{\mathbf{A}}, \quad (\text{B5})$$

$$\frac{P_{\text{out}}^x(y|x)}{P_{\text{out}}(y|x)} = \left\langle \frac{1}{\Delta}(y - f(x; \mathbf{A}))f'(x; \mathbf{A}) \right\rangle_{\mathbf{A}}, \quad (\text{B6})$$

$$\frac{P_{\text{out}}^{yy}(y|x)}{P_{\text{out}}(y|x)} = \left\langle \frac{1}{\Delta^2}(y - f(x; \mathbf{A}))^2 \right\rangle_{\mathbf{A}} - \frac{1}{\Delta}, \quad (\text{B7})$$

$$\frac{P_{\text{out}}^{yx}(y|x)}{P_{\text{out}}(y|x)} = \left\langle -\frac{1}{\Delta^2}(y - f(x; \mathbf{A}))^2 f'(x; \mathbf{A}) + \frac{1}{\Delta} f'(x; \mathbf{A}) \right\rangle_{\mathbf{A}}, \quad (\text{B8})$$

$$\frac{P_{\text{out}}^{xx}(y|x)}{P_{\text{out}}(y|x)} = \left\langle \left(\frac{1}{\Delta^2}(y - f(x; \mathbf{A}))^2 - \frac{1}{\Delta} \right) f'(x; \mathbf{A})^2 + \frac{1}{\Delta}(y - f(x; \mathbf{A}))f''(x; \mathbf{A}) \right\rangle_{\mathbf{A}}. \quad (\text{B9})$$

Since all expressions have a similar form we will treat only the last one, all others can be bounded in the same way. We have

$$\left| \frac{P_{\text{out}}^{xx}(y|x)}{P_{\text{out}}(y|x)} \right| \leq \left\langle \left(\frac{1}{\Delta^2}(y - f(x; \mathbf{A}))^2 + \frac{1}{\Delta} \right) f'(x; \mathbf{A})^2 \right\rangle_{\mathbf{A}} + \left\langle \frac{1}{\Delta} |y - f(x; \mathbf{A})| |f''(x; \mathbf{A})| \right\rangle_{\mathbf{A}}. \quad (\text{B10})$$

When $y = f(S_{t\mu}; \mathbf{A}_\mu) + \sqrt{\Delta}Z_\mu$, since f is bounded along with its first two derivatives (see [H2](#)) we obtain immediately

$$\left| \frac{P_{\text{out}}^{xx}(y|x)}{P_{\text{out}}(y|x)} \right| \leq C(f)(|Z_\mu|^2 + 1). \quad (\text{B11})$$

\square

Remark 5. With such bound one can see that after averaging such ratios (with or without $\langle \cdot \rangle$ as in [\(44\)](#)) with respect to Z_μ , we simply obtain a uniform bound $C(f)$.

Now let us return to the proof of Lemma 5.

Proof of Lemma 5. By definition one has $\mathbb{E}[u'_{Y_{t_\mu}}(S_{t_\mu}) | S_{t_\mu}] = \int dy P_{\text{out}}^x(y | S_{t_\mu}) = 0$. For $U_{\mu\nu}$ instead, we first need to realize that $U_{\mu\mu} = P_{\text{out}}^{xx}(Y_{t_\mu} | S_{t_\mu}) / P_{\text{out}}(Y_{t_\mu} | S_{t_\mu})$ which implies $\mathbb{E}[U_{\mu\mu} | S_{t_\mu}] = \int dy P_{\text{out}}^{xx}(y | S_{t_\mu}) = 0$. Concerning the off-diagonal instead, conditionally on S_{t_μ}, S_{t_ν} the remaining disorder in the Y 's is independent, so for $\mu \neq \nu$ we have $\mathbb{E}[U_{\mu\nu} | S_{t_\mu}, S_{t_\nu}] = \int dy P_{\text{out}}^x(y | S_{t_\mu}) \int dy' P_{\text{out}}^x(y' | S_{t_\nu}) = 0$. For the boundedness of the derivatives it is sufficient to notice that

$$(u'_{Y_{t_\mu}}(S_{t_\mu}))^2 = \left(\frac{P_{\text{out}}^x(Y_{t_\mu} | S_{t_\mu})}{P_{\text{out}}(Y_{t_\mu} | S_{t_\mu})} \right)^2 \leq C(f)(|Z_\mu|^4 + 1), \quad (\text{B12})$$

the last inequality being true due to Lemma 18 and the fact that $Y_{t_\mu} = f(S_{t_\mu}; \mathbf{A}_\mu) + \sqrt{\Delta} Z_\mu$. Now it is immediate that after taking the expectation conditioned on S_{t_μ} we obtain a bound $C(f)$. In order to deal with the last quantity $U_{\mu\nu}^2$ we rewrite

$$U_{\mu\nu}^2 = \left(\delta_{\mu\nu} \left(\frac{P_{\text{out}}^{xx}(Y_{t_\mu} | S_{t_\mu})}{P_{\text{out}}(Y_{t_\mu} | S_{t_\mu})} - \left(\frac{P_{\text{out}}^x(Y_{t_\mu} | S_{t_\mu})}{P_{\text{out}}(Y_{t_\mu} | S_{t_\mu})} \right)^2 \right) + \frac{P_{\text{out}}^x(Y_{t_\mu} | S_{t_\mu})}{P_{\text{out}}(Y_{t_\mu} | S_{t_\mu})} \frac{P_{\text{out}}^x(Y_{t_\nu} | S_{t_\nu})}{P_{\text{out}}(Y_{t_\nu} | S_{t_\nu})} \right)^2.$$

With the help of Lemma 18 one can see immediately that $U_{\mu\nu}^2 \leq C(f)P(Z_{t_\mu}, Z_{t_\nu})$, where P is some polynomial with even degrees. Once again, after taking expectation we get a bound by a positive constant $C(f)$. □

Appendix C Proof of Lemma 6

We recall the statement for the reader's convenience.

Lemma 19 (Approximations). *Recall $\rho := \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)}\varphi'$ and $\epsilon^2 := \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)}\varphi^2 - \rho^2$. Let $\tilde{\varphi}$ be either φ or the identity function. Under assumptions (H1) and (H2) the following estimates hold:*

$$\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*}\varphi'(\alpha_{\mu i}) = \rho + O\left(\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_\mu\|^2}{d} - 1\right), \quad (\text{C13})$$

$$\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*}\varphi^2(\alpha_{\mu i}) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)}\varphi^2 + O\left(\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_\mu\|^2}{d} - 1\right), \quad (\text{C14})$$

$$\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*}\varphi(\alpha_{\mu i})\tilde{\varphi}(\alpha_{\nu i}) = \rho\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)}\tilde{\varphi}'\frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top\mathbf{X}_\nu}{d} + O\left(\left(\frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top\mathbf{X}_\nu}{\|\mathbf{X}_\nu\|^2}\right)^2\right) + O\left(\frac{(\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top\mathbf{X}_\nu)^2}{\|\mathbf{X}_\nu\|^2d}\right) + O\left(\frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top\mathbf{X}_\nu}{d}\left(\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_\mu\|^2}{d} - 1\right)\right), \quad (\text{C15})$$

$$\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*}\varphi'(\alpha_{\mu i})\varphi'(\alpha_{\nu i}) = \rho^2 + O\left(\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_\mu\|^2}{d} - 1\right) + O\left(\frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top\mathbf{X}_\nu}{\|\mathbf{X}_\nu\|^2}\right), \quad (\text{C16})$$

$$\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*}\varphi^2(\alpha_{\mu i})\tilde{\varphi}^2(\alpha_{\nu i}) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)}\varphi^2\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)}\tilde{\varphi}^2 + O\left(\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_\mu\|^2}{d} - 1\right) + O\left(\frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top\mathbf{X}_\nu}{\|\mathbf{X}_\nu\|^2}\right). \quad (\text{C17})$$

Proof. To begin with, we need to control $\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*}\varphi(\alpha_{\mu i})$:

$$|\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*}\varphi(\alpha_{\mu i})| = |\mathbb{E}_z\left[\varphi\left(z\sqrt{\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_\mu\|^2}{d}}\right) - \varphi(z)\right]| \leq c\mathbb{E}_z|z|\left|\sqrt{\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_\mu\|^2}{d}} - 1\right| = O\left(\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_\mu\|^2}{d} - 1\right), \quad (\text{C18})$$

where we used Lipschitzness of φ and, crucially, that $\mathbb{E}_z\varphi(z) = 0$.

Let us move to (C13). We can use also Lipschitzness of φ' , as it has bounded derivative:

$$|\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*}\varphi'(\alpha_{\mu i}) - \rho| = |\mathbb{E}_z\left[\varphi'\left(z\sqrt{\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_\mu\|^2}{d}}\right) - \varphi'(z)\right]| \leq K\mathbb{E}_z|z|\left|\sqrt{\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_\mu\|^2}{d}} - 1\right| = O\left(\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_\mu\|^2}{d} - 1\right). \quad (\text{C19})$$

With analogous steps one can prove (C14):

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \tilde{\varphi}^2(\alpha_{\mu i}) - \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)} \tilde{\varphi}^2| &= |\mathbb{E}_z \left[\tilde{\varphi}^2 \left(z \sqrt{\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_\mu\|^2}{d}} \right) - \tilde{\varphi}^2(z) \right]| \\ &\leq \mathbb{E}_z \left| \tilde{\varphi} \left(z \sqrt{\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_\mu\|^2}{d}} \right) - \tilde{\varphi}(z) \right| \left| \tilde{\varphi} \left(z \sqrt{\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_\mu\|^2}{d}} \right) + \tilde{\varphi}(z) \right| \leq \tilde{c}^2 \mathbb{E}_z z^2 \left| \frac{\|\mathbf{X}_\mu\|^2}{d} - 1 \right| = O\left(\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_\mu\|^2}{d} - 1\right), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C20})$$

where \tilde{c} is the Lipschitz constant for $\tilde{\varphi}$.

Consider now (C15). In what follows we drop the i -index for brevity. Let

$$\alpha_{\mu\perp\nu} := \alpha_\mu - \alpha_\nu \frac{\mathbb{E} \alpha_\mu \alpha_\nu}{\mathbb{E}^2 \alpha_\nu} = \alpha_\mu - \alpha_\nu \frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{\|\mathbf{X}_\nu\|^2},$$

that is independent of α_ν . Now we expand φ around $\alpha_{\mu\perp\nu}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi(\alpha_\mu) \tilde{\varphi}(\alpha_\nu) &= \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi(\alpha_{\mu\perp\nu}) \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \tilde{\varphi}(\alpha_\nu) + \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi'(\alpha_{\mu\perp\nu}) \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \tilde{\varphi}'(\alpha_\nu) \frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{d} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi''(p) \tilde{\varphi}(\alpha_\nu) \alpha_\nu^2 \left(\frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{\|\mathbf{X}_\nu\|^2} \right)^2. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C21})$$

p is a point in between $\alpha_{\mu\perp\nu}$ and α_ν . If φ were odd, the first term would be zero. Here we need to treat it separately, as discussed in (C18), which would yield:

$$\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi(\alpha_{\mu\perp\nu}) = \mathbb{E}_z \varphi \left(z \sqrt{\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_\mu\|^2}{d} - \frac{(\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu)^2}{d \|\mathbf{X}_\nu\|^2}} \right) = O\left(\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_\mu\|^2}{d} - 1\right) + O\left(\frac{(\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu)^2}{d \|\mathbf{X}_\nu\|^2}\right), \quad (\text{C22})$$

$$\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi(\alpha_\nu) = O\left(\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_\nu\|^2}{d} - 1\right) \quad (\text{C23})$$

Now we expand again $\varphi'(\alpha_{\mu\perp\nu})$ around the initial point α_μ :

$$\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi'(\alpha_{\mu\perp\nu}) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi'(\alpha_\mu) - \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi''(p) \alpha_\nu \frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{\|\mathbf{X}_\nu\|^2} = \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi'(\alpha_\mu) + O\left(\frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{\|\mathbf{X}_\nu\|^2}\right) \quad (\text{C24})$$

where p has the same meaning as before, and we used $\varphi'' \leq \bar{K}$. At this point it suffices to use (C13) on $\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi'(\alpha_\mu)$ and $\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \tilde{\varphi}'(\alpha_\nu)$ and the estimate is proved.

Let us move to (C16). As for the previous point, we follow the orthogonalization procedure:

$$\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi'(\alpha_\mu) \varphi'(\alpha_\nu) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi'(\alpha_{\mu\perp\nu}) \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi'(\alpha_\nu) + \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi''(p) \varphi'(\alpha_\nu) \alpha_\nu \frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{\|\mathbf{X}_\nu\|^2} \quad (\text{C25})$$

$$= \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi'(\alpha_{\mu\perp\nu}) \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi'(\alpha_\nu) + O\left(\frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{\|\mathbf{X}_\nu\|^2}\right). \quad (\text{C26})$$

Now we use (C24) and (C13) to conclude:

$$\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi'(\alpha_\mu) \varphi'(\alpha_\nu) = \rho^2 + O\left(\frac{\|\mathbf{X}_\mu\|^2}{d} - 1\right) + O\left(\frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{\|\mathbf{X}_\nu\|^2}\right) \quad (\text{C27})$$

as in the statement.

Now we move to (C17). As before, we expand $\varphi^2(\alpha_\mu)$ around $\alpha_{\mu\perp\nu}$:

$$\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi^2(\alpha_\mu) \tilde{\varphi}^2(\alpha_\nu) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi^2(\alpha_{\mu\perp\nu}) \tilde{\varphi}^2(\alpha_\nu) + 2 \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \int_0^1 ds \varphi(\alpha_{\mu,\nu}(s)) \varphi'(\alpha_{\mu,\nu}(s)) \tilde{\varphi}^2(\alpha_\nu) \alpha_\nu \frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{\|\mathbf{X}_\nu\|^2} \quad (\text{C28})$$

where $\alpha_{\mu,\nu}(s) = \alpha_{\mu\perp\nu} + s\alpha_\nu \mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu / \|\mathbf{X}_\nu\|^2$. The integral on the r.h.s. can be bounded in different ways. For instance, one can first integrate the α_ν by part, recalling that $\alpha_{\mu\perp\nu}$ is independent of it, and then exploit the fact that both φ and $\tilde{\varphi}$ are Lipschitz. This yields the $O(\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu / \|\mathbf{X}_\nu\|^2)$ in the statement.

The leading term $\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi^2(\alpha_{\mu\perp\nu}) \tilde{\varphi}^2(\alpha_\nu)$ can be split into $\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi^2(\alpha_{\mu\perp\nu}) \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \tilde{\varphi}^2(\alpha_\nu)$ thanks to the orthogonalization. Expanding $\varphi^2(\alpha_{\mu\perp\nu})$ around α_μ we get

$$\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi^2(\alpha_{\mu\perp\nu}) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi^2(\alpha_\mu) - 2 \int_0^1 ds \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi(\alpha_{\mu,\nu}(s)) \varphi'(\alpha_{\mu,\nu}(s)) \alpha_\nu \frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{\|\mathbf{X}_\nu\|^2} \quad (\text{C29})$$

with $\alpha_{\mu,\nu}(s)$ as above. The integral contributes again with the same order as the one above, therefore

$$\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi^2(\alpha_\mu) \tilde{\varphi}^2(\alpha_\nu) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \varphi^2(\alpha_\mu) \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*} \tilde{\varphi}^2(\alpha_\nu) + O\left(\frac{\mathbf{X}_\mu^\top \mathbf{X}_\nu}{\|\mathbf{X}_\nu\|^2}\right). \quad (\text{C30})$$

Finally, it only remains to apply (C14) to both the factors in the leading contribution on the r.h.s., which yields the missing remainder $O(\|\mathbf{X}_\mu\|^2/d - 1)$ in the statement. \square

Appendix D Bound of the constant in Theorem 7

Here we aim to give more detailed description of the constant $C(f, \varphi)$ that appears in Theorem 7. For this we start with Lemma 18. Following its proof one can easily see that absolute values of r.h.s. of (B5)-(B9) can be bounded by

$$\left| \frac{P_{\text{out}}^y(y|x)}{P_{\text{out}}(y|x)} \right| \leq c\Delta^{-1/2}, \quad (\text{D31})$$

$$\left| \frac{P_{\text{out}}^x(y|x)}{P_{\text{out}}(y|x)} \right| \leq c\Delta^{-1/2} \|f'\|_\infty, \quad (\text{D32})$$

$$\left| \frac{P_{\text{out}}^{yy}(y|x)}{P_{\text{out}}(y|x)} \right| \leq c\Delta^{-1}, \quad (\text{D33})$$

$$\left| \frac{P_{\text{out}}^{yx}(y|x)}{P_{\text{out}}(y|x)} \right| \leq c\Delta^{-1} \|f'\|_\infty, \quad (\text{D34})$$

$$\left| \frac{P_{\text{out}}^{xx}(y|x)}{P_{\text{out}}(y|x)} \right| \leq \Delta^{-1} \|f'\|_\infty^2 + \Delta^{-1/2} \|f''\|_\infty. \quad (\text{D35})$$

Returning to the proof of Theorem 7, we specify the bounds from Lemmas 14-16. We start with Lemma 14 and show

$$\mathbb{E} \left(\frac{1}{n} \log \mathcal{Z}_t - \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}, \xi^*, \mathbf{z}} \frac{1}{n} \log \mathcal{Z}_t \right)^2 \leq \frac{c}{n} (1 + \Delta^{-1} \|f'\|_\infty^2 + \Delta^{-1} \|f'\|_\infty^2 \|\varphi'\|_\infty^2). \quad (\text{D36})$$

The above bound can be obtained by following the steps of the initial proof and using inequalities (D31)-(D35) instead of Lemma 18.

In the proof of Lemma 15 we don't require any changes till the last step, where we bound r.h.s. of inequalities (120) and (121). Here we use only the fact that f is bounded, so we immediately obtain $|H - H'| \leq c\|f\|_\infty^2$. From what follows

$$\mathbb{E} \left(\frac{1}{n} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{z}, \xi^*} \log \mathcal{Z}_t - \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{A}} \frac{1}{n} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{z}, \xi^*} \log \mathcal{Z}_t \right)^2 \leq \frac{c}{n} \|f\|_\infty^2. \quad (\text{D37})$$

Finally, in the proof of Lemma 16 instead of (D38) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
\left| \frac{\partial g}{\partial W_{ij}^*} \right| &\leq \frac{C_1(f, \varphi)}{\sqrt{d}} \mathbb{E}_\psi \left| \frac{(\mathbf{a}^* \circ \varphi'(\frac{\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}}) \mathbf{W}^*)_j}{\sqrt{pd}} \frac{a_i^*}{\sqrt{p}} \right| + \frac{C_1(f, \varphi)}{\sqrt{d}} \mathbb{E}_\psi \left| \frac{v_j^*}{\sqrt{d}} \frac{a_i^*}{\sqrt{p}} \right| \\
&\quad + \frac{C_2(f, \varphi)}{\sqrt{d}} \mathbb{E}_\psi \left| (|Z_\mu|^2 + 1) \frac{a_i^*}{\sqrt{p}} \left\langle \frac{(\mathbf{a} \circ \varphi'(\frac{\mathbf{W} \mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}}) \mathbf{W})_j}{\sqrt{pd}} \right\rangle \right| \\
&\quad + \frac{C_2(f, \varphi)}{\sqrt{d}} \mathbb{E}_\psi \left| (|Z_\mu|^2 + 1) \frac{a_i^*}{\sqrt{p}} \left\langle \frac{v_j}{\sqrt{d}} \right\rangle \right| + \frac{C_3(f, \varphi)}{\sqrt{d}} \mathbb{E}_\psi \left| \frac{a_i^* W_{ij}^*}{\sqrt{pd}} \right|, \quad (\text{D38})
\end{aligned}$$

where

$$C_1(f, \varphi) = c \|\varphi'\|_\infty (\Delta^{-1} \|f'\|_\infty^2 + \Delta^{-1/2} \|f''\|_\infty) \quad (\text{D39})$$

$$C_2(f, \varphi) = c \Delta^{-1} \|\varphi'\|_\infty \|f'\|_\infty^2 \quad (\text{D40})$$

$$C_3(f, \varphi) = c \|\varphi''\|_\infty \|f'\|_\infty \quad (\text{D41})$$

Repeating the following steps of the original proof and taking into account that $C_2(f, \varphi) \leq C_1(f, \varphi)$ we obtain in the end

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{i,j}^{p,d} \mathbb{E} \left| \frac{\partial g}{\partial W_{ij}^*} \right|^2 &\leq \frac{1}{d} \left(C_1^2(f, \varphi) \mathbb{E}^{1/2} \left[\frac{\|\mathbf{a}^* \circ \varphi'(\frac{\mathbf{W}^* \mathbf{X}_\mu}{\sqrt{d}}) \mathbf{W}^*\|^4}{p^2 d^2} \right] + (C_1^2(f, \varphi) + C_3^2(f, \varphi)) \right) \\
&\leq \frac{1}{d} (C_1^2(f, \varphi) (1 + \|\varphi'\|_\infty^4) + C_3^2(f, \varphi)) \leq \frac{c}{d} \left((\Delta^{-1} \|f'\|_\infty^2 + \Delta^{-1/2} \|f''\|_\infty)^2 (1 + \|\varphi'\|_\infty^4)^2 + \|\varphi''\|_\infty^2 \|f'\|_\infty^2 \right).
\end{aligned}$$

For the expression with partial derivatives with respect of v_i^* we get the very similar bound

$$\sum_i^d \mathbb{E} \left| \frac{\partial g}{\partial v_i^*} \right|^2 \leq \frac{c}{d} (\Delta^{-1} \|f'\|_\infty^2 + \Delta^{-1/2} \|f''\|_\infty)^2 (1 + \|\varphi'\|_\infty^4). \quad (\text{D42})$$

Last two inequalities give more precise bound in Lemma 16

$$\mathbb{E}(g - \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{W}^*, \mathbf{v}^*} g)^2 \leq \frac{c}{d} \left((\Delta^{-1} \|f'\|_\infty^2 + \Delta^{-1/2} \|f''\|_\infty)^2 (1 + \|\varphi'\|_\infty^4)^2 + \|\varphi''\|_\infty^2 \|f'\|_\infty^2 \right). \quad (\text{D43})$$

Combining all above we can restate Theorem 7 as

Proposition 20. *Under assumptions (H1) and (H2) there exists a non-negative general constant c independent from all the parameters of the model such that*

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{a}^*} \mathbb{V}_{\mathbf{a}^*} \left(\frac{1}{n} \log Z_t \right) &= \mathbb{E} \left(\frac{1}{n} \log Z_t - \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{a}^*} \frac{1}{n} \log Z_t \right)^2 \leq c \left(\frac{1}{d} + \frac{1}{n} \right) \times \\
&\max\{ (\Delta^{-1} \|f'\|_\infty^2 + \Delta^{-1/2} \|f''\|_\infty)^2 (1 + \|\varphi'\|_\infty^4)^2 + \|\varphi''\|_\infty^2 \|f'\|_\infty^2, \|f\|_\infty^2, 1 + \Delta^{-1} \|f'\|_\infty^2 (1 + \|\varphi'\|_\infty^2) \}.
\end{aligned}$$

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